

Capacity Development Modules

ToT workshops in designing transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes

29 September 2025

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| 9. GENILLARD & Co GMBH | 18. SEI OXFORD OFFICE LIMITED |

Report Overview

Project number	101073978
Project acronym	DIRECTED
Project name	Disaster Resilience for Extreme Climate Events providing Interoperable Data, Models, Communication and Governance
Call	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-02
Type of action	HORIZON Innovation Action
Responsible service	European Research Executive Agency
Project starting date	01/10/2022
Project duration	4 Years
Period covered	1 October 2022–29 September 2025
Reporting period number	RP2

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	05.09.2025	First full draft
2.0	15.09.2025	WP 3/WP 4 Internal review
3.0	26.09.2025	Consortium partners internal review
4.0	29.09.2025	Final edit for submission

Executive Summary

This deliverable documents the development of the co-production capacity-building modules within the DIRECTED project, which aims to strengthen Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) through improved knowledge co-production processes, the results of this work are available to explore here: <https://weadapt.org/tandem/>

At the core of these modules is the Tandem Framework (Daniels et al., 2020), a structured approach to transdisciplinary knowledge co-production that has been implemented across multiple European Real World Labs (RWLs) and embedded within the application of the Risk-Tandem (Parviainen et al., 2024), integrating collaborative governance within CCA and DRR decision-making. Risk-Tandem builds on the foundation of the knowledge co-production process, introducing other risk governance mechanisms and tools (D3.2).

The process of carrying out knowledge co-production both develops the capacity of its participants and also identifies new capacity needs. This has enabled the development of context- and user-driven training workshops and capacity development modules with each RWL. Needs have been identified through iterative scoping consultations, qualitative analyses of RWL reports and Capacity Needs Assessments. These activities revealed the importance of developing four key capacities: collaborative, creative, and reflexive, and systems thinking, supported by skills in design, research, and facilitation (Cumiskey et al. 2025). Training-of-Trainer (ToT) workshops, capacity development modules and supporting materials were designed and applied in the labs based on these insights. This report reviews the outcomes of these processes. While participants initially reported limited confidence in applying structured design methods, facilitation techniques, and systems thinking, their capabilities improved considerably through training, peer-to-peer exchanges, and iterative co-design processes, enabling ‘learning-by-doing’ (Dewey, 1971). The findings underscore the need for stronger integration of DRM and CCA, greater emphasis on citizen engagement beyond communication, strengthened representation in governance, and improved approaches to managing uncertainty and ensuring data interoperability. Monitoring, evaluation, and reflexivity also emerged as essential elements that must be embedded as ongoing practices rather than treated as retrospective assessments.

Building on these insights, DIRECTED has updated the online Tandem guidance to be an interactive tool, enabling easier navigation of the Tandem Guiding Questions. Alongside this, DIRECTED has produced a set of interactive Tandem Capacity Development Modules and toolbox of facilitation canvases. This approach responds to the recognition that Tandem questions, although thorough, require creative, accessible, and inclusive ways of being unpacked and explored by practitioners. The Modules build on lessons from the iterative application of Tandem in DIRECTED, ultimately translating project-specific training that targeted RWL hosts into practical guidance for a wider audience of practitioners and policymakers. The resulting modules can be accessed as printable PDFs for in-person

facilitation or via Miro for online delivery. These modules will form part of the wider DIRECTED e-Learning Platform (D6.3) targeting DRM and CCA professionals.

Looking forward, DIRECTED will continue to strengthen the Tandem framework by embedding futures' thinking, expanding consideration around citizen participation, and institutionalizing reflexive and peer-to-peer learning. The online guidance will be enhanced by an interactive glossary (or taxonomy, D2.2) for improved interoperability and communication. Building on experiences such as the Zala Real World Lab workshops, Tandem also now incorporates exercises that align individual and collective goals, drawing on principles from community organizing to ensure that collaborations are inclusive, trust-based, and beneficial to all stakeholders.

Through these efforts, DIRECTED contributes to building the skills, tools, and collaborative practices needed to navigate the complex challenges of climate resilience and risk governance.

Ethical considerations

1 Free and informed consent:

Data has been collected in Real World Labs (RWLs) by their Host organizations (either workshop reports, interviews, or meeting minutes). Participants of the stakeholders have signed a participation agreement and informed consent form as a part of the DIRECTED process.

2 Right of life and Human Dignity:

The Tandem framework emphasizes that the right to life and the preservation of human dignity must serve as foundational principles in risk governance. It addresses gaps in existing governance approaches by moving beyond tokenistic consultation to ensure the meaningful inclusion of vulnerable and marginalized populations as both knowledge-holders and decision-makers. This commitment recognizes that lived experience provides critical insight for responsible and equitable governance.

To support this, the Tandem modules integrate reflexivity as a core capacity for co-production. Reflexive guidance questions and processes are embedded to encourage continuous reflection on whose voices are heard, whose rights are protected, and how decisions affect the most at-risk groups. By explicitly introducing questions of life and dignity into RWL processes and engagements, the framework expands risk governance beyond standard procedural approaches, grounding it in ethical responsibility and shared humanity.

3 Diversity, fairness and no discrimination:

The Tandem framework recognizes that diversity strengthens co-production and that fairness requires more than formal inclusion. Its modules critically examine the spaces and processes of engagement, questioning how power operates within them and working to prevent discrimination in both participation and outcomes.

4 Privacy and Data Governance:

Aligned with DIRECTED internal processes; data is stored by the Braunschweig University (Nextcloud). Additionally, AtlasTi (licensed by SEI) was used to thematically code RWL documents and transcripts.

5 Research Integrity:

The Framework has been co-designed based on iterative practical application (Daniels et al., 2020), with a specific focus on upscaling and further use (Bharwani et al., 2024).

6 Social and Environmental Impact:

The Tandem modules are grounded in the recognition that social, cultural, political and environmental dimensions are inseparable in risk governance. Its modules apply a systems thinking approach to reveal the interconnected impacts of decisions on communities and ecosystems across scales. This perspective emphasizes not only present complexities but also intergenerational responsibility, ensuring that co-production processes support long-term sustainability and collective well-being.

Contents

Table of Figures.....	8
Index of Tables.....	10
List of Abbreviations.....	11
1 Introduction.....	12
2 Method and Approach.....	13
2.1 Iterative application of Tandem.....	13
2.2 Coding.....	14
2.2.1 Development of the codebook.....	16
2.2.1.1 MEL-Based Deductive Coding.....	16
2.2.1.2 Inductive Coding.....	16
2.2.1.3 Framework Structure.....	16
2.2.1.4 Coding of RWL Outputs.....	17
2.2.2 Coding framework implementation.....	17
3. Findings.....	18
3.1 Capacity Needs Assessment.....	18
3.1.1 Design.....	18
3.1.2 Research.....	20
3.1.3 Facilitation.....	21
3.1.4 Collaboration.....	23
3.1.5 Systems Thinking.....	24
3.1.6 Reflexivity.....	26
3.1.7 Creativity.....	28
3.2 Evaluating the co-production process.....	30
3.2.1 Integration of DRR and CCA.....	30
3.2.2 Multi-hazard and legacy risk management approach.....	32
3.2.3 Citizen engagement.....	34
3.2.4 Communicating uncertainty and Data interoperability.....	35
3.2.5 Capacity development.....	36
3.2.6 Monitoring, evaluation, and learning.....	37
4 Tandem online modules update.....	38
4.1 Developing Tandem Modules.....	39
4.1.1 Overview Module.....	40
4.1.2 Phase 1: Foundation Module.....	41
4.1.2.1 Tandem challenges and goals scoping canvas.....	41
4.1.2.2 Risk governance scoping canvas.....	42
4.1.2.3 Tandem stakeholder analysis canvas.....	44
4.1.2.4 Net-Map exercise.....	45
4.1.2.5 Stakeholder Excel.....	47
4.1.2.6 Tandem aligning and trust building.....	48
4.1.2.7 Capacities and needs assessment.....	49
4.1.2.8 Theory of change.....	52
4.1.3 Phase 2: Co-exploring ‘What is...’ Module.....	52
4.1.3.1 Co-exploring stakeholders.....	53
4.1.3.2 Multi Layer Perspective Mapping.....	54
4.1.3.3 Multi Layer Perspective Mapping - Identifying potential leverage points..	56
5 Next steps.....	56
5.1 Futures thinking.....	57

5.2 Citizen engagement.....	58
5.3 Taxonomy development.....	59
5.4 Monitoring, evaluation, and learning.....	60
References.....	61
Annex 1 Structured capacity needs assessment.....	63

Table of Figures

Figure 1 : Capacity Needs Assessment Design Skills Results.	19
Figure 2 : Capacity Needs Assessment Research Skills Results.	20
Figure 3 : Capacity Needs Assessment Facilitation Skills Results.	21
Figure 4 : Capacity Needs Assessment Collaborative Capacity Results.	23
Figure 5 : Capacity Needs Assessment Systems Thinking Capacity Results.	25
Figure 6 : Capacity Needs Assessment Reflexive Capacity Results.	26
Figure 7 : Capacity Needs Assessment Creative Capacity Results.	28
Figure 8 : Overview of the Tandem capacity development training modules.	40
Figure 9 : Canvas of Challenges and Goals scoping exercise used in Zala RWL 3 workshops March 2025	41
Figure 10 : Tandem Modules resource: Tandem Challenges and Goals Scoping Canvas	43
Figure 11 : Capacity Development Risk Governance scoping Miro exercise, June 2023	43
Figure 12 : Tandem Modules resource: Risk Governance Scoping Canvas	44
Figure 13 : Adaptation of Mendelow’s power-interest matrix, Capacity Development, January 2024	44
Figure 14 : Tandem Modules resource: Tandem Stakeholder Analysis Canvas	46
Figure 15 : Examples of Net-Maps, January 2024	47
Figure 16 : Tandem Modules resource: Net-Map exercise	47
Figure 17 : Stakeholder Engagement Excel Guidance Note on Stakeholder Selection for RWL set-up, January 2024	48
Figure 18 : Tandem Modules resource: Stakeholder Excel	48
Figure 19 : Canvas of Aligning exercise used in Zala RWL 3 workshops March 2025	49
Figure 20 : Tandem Modules resource: Tandem Aligning and Trust Building	49
Figure 21 : Capacities Exercise use in RWL 1 workshop, March 2023	51
Figure 22 : Tandem Modules resource: Capacities and Needs Assessment	50

Figure 23 : Tandem Modules resource: Establishing Ways of Working	52
Figure 24 : Canvas of Theory of Change exercise used in Zala RWL 3 workshops March 2025	53
Figure 25 : Tandem Modules resource: Theory of Change	53
Figure 26&27 : Target group and solution co-exploration exercise used in ToT RiskTandem training in March 2024 at the DIRECTED General Assembly	55
Figure 28 : Tandem Modules resource: Co-Exploring Stakeholders	54
Figure 29 : Multi Layer Perspective map exercise, capacity development session, January 2025	55
Figure 30 : Tandem Modules resource: Historical Evolution Multi Layer Perspective Map	55
Figure 31 : Multi Layer Perspective map exercises, capacity development session, January 2025	57
Figure 32 : Tandem Modules resource: Identifying Leverage Points Multi Layer Perspective Map	57

Index of Tables

[Table 1](#): The combination of Tandem guiding questions categorized under sub-code themes, and the “good principles” of co-production, providing a categorisation scheme to evaluate successes and challenges of co-production in RWLs.

16

List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
CAS	COMPLEX ADAPTIVE SYSTEMS
CCA	CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION
DRM	DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT
DRR	DISASTER RISK REDUCTION
MEL	MONITORING, EVALUATION, AND LEARNING
RWL	REAL WORLD LAB
ToT	TRAINING OF TRAINERS

1 Introduction

The Tandem Framework (Daniels et al., 2020) and its subsequent update (Bharwani et al, 2024) has undergone further refinement throughout the DIRECTED project, as it has been applied and adapted within each of the Real World Labs (RWLs). Originally developed as a guidance tool to co-design climate services in several geographic and decision contexts, Tandem has now been implemented to support similar engagement and decision-making across new and diverse European contexts.

The purpose of this deliverable is to: review the application of the capacity development processes required to implement Tandem Framework by RWLs, then upscaling this application to a wider group of stakeholders; assess the application of Tandem within DIRECTED, identifying gaps in its current application; and, outline how these insights have informed the development of Tandem and the Tandem Capacity Development Modules for a broader audience of Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) and Disaster Risk Management (DRM) professionals. The results of this work aims to support the refinement of Tandem (D4.3) to better meet the evolving needs of the CCA and DRM fields and provide updated guidance for its implementation in the final phases of the project. The Tandem capacity development process and modules sit within the Risk-Tandem Framework application (see Deliverable 3.2) to enable the RWL hosts to effectively deliver knowledge co-production across the Foundation, Growth, Learn and Sustain Phases to address context-specific DRM/CCA challenges by scoping, co-exploring, co-designing and integrating governance and technical solutions for DRM/ CCA.

The Tandem online capacity development modules build on lessons learned through a combination of:

- The iterative application of Tandem in DIRECTED
- Ongoing scoping consultations with the labs
- Analysis of the results of the capacity needs assessment
- DIRECTED document and reports coding analysis
- The foundation and insights from the ToT workshop preparation and training sessions (including guidance documents, presentations, literature, and hands-on activities),
- Resources created and used in the RWLs

As a result, we have developed a comprehensive set of Capacity Development Modules for Tandem (which can be printed as PDFs for in-person facilitation or accessed on Miro for online delivery), and an updated online interactive Tandem tool, designed for easier click-through navigation of Tandem questions. All are available to explore here: <https://weadapt.org/tandem/>

The purpose of these modules is to translate the tailored, project-specific training and diversity of approaches taken by RWL hosts into a format that can be applied more widely, beyond the DIRECTED project.

The structure of this report reflects this process. First, discussing the results of the Capacity Needs Assessment. Secondly, the analysis of the coding of the DIRECTED reports and documents. Finally, showing how the recommendations of these have been combined with foundation and insights from the ToT workshop preparation, and training sessions, to adapt resources created and used in the RWLs to update Tandem through the development of the Tandem online capacity development modules.

2 Method and Approach

This review adopts a threefold approach, combining reflective insights from the iterative application of the Tandem Framework (M1 - 36) with a structured qualitative analysis of RWL documentation and outputs, complimented by Capacity Needs Assessments ([Annex 1](#)). This methodology aims to capture the capacity development needs of RWL hosts and both the practical evolution of the Tandem framework and empirical evidence of its implementation. With this basis, we provide recommendations for the update of Tandem and how these can be met through the Tandem Capacity Development Modules (www.weadapt.org/tandem).

2.1 Iterative application of Tandem

Throughout the DIRECTED project, the Tandem Framework has been applied iteratively within each RWL. This has allowed its continual refinement and tailoring to diverse European contexts. The iterative process has not only tested the framework's flexibility but also informed its ongoing development, particularly through the co-design of training materials, ongoing support for RWL hosts, and collaborative planning of RWL engagements.

To support effective application of Tandem by RWL hosts, we began with scoping consultations. These initial engagements aimed at understanding the specific contexts, needs, and priorities of each RWL. They promoted equitable, trust-based relationships and guided the co-development of training strategies. An overview of the RWL consultations can be found in Annex 1 of D3.2. Building on these one on one scoping consultations, a dynamic Training of Trainers (ToT) programme was developed. This combined online and in-person workshops, detailed guidance materials, and tailored one-on-one consultations. The ToT activities were designed to build RWL hosts' capacities to implement co-production processes using the Tandem Framework, drawing from the following components:

Based on scoping insights, literature, and practical experience from RWLs, four core co-production capacities were identified and have been further expanded in Cumiskey et al. (2025):

- Collaborative Capacity: foundational to sustaining inclusive, transdisciplinary processes;
- Systems Thinking Capacity: for understanding complexity and interconnections;
- Creative Capacity: to foster innovative, adaptive solutions;
- Reflexive Capacity: to support critical thinking and learning throughout the process.

Each capacity is associated with specific Design, Research, and Facilitation skills necessary to implement the four phases of the Tandem Framework: scoping and review, co-exploration, co-design, and integration.

Following this, a structured framework (see [Annex 1](#)) was regularly used to evaluate RWL hosts' existing skills and evolving development needs. The assessment explored understanding, perceived value, and self-assessed capabilities for each core capacity (Collaborative, Systems Thinking, Creative, Reflexive) and skill (Design, Research, Facilitation), their continuing needs from the project, as well as reflections on the relevance and effectiveness of the DIRECTED training.

Opportunities for mutual learning were built into the program through facilitated peer-to-peer learning exchanges. These sessions allowed RWL hosts to share challenges, strategies, and insights with one another, fostering a community of practice.

After each ToT session, the project team collaborated with RWL hosts to adapt training content and workshop design to their specific needs. This process was supported by post-workshop debriefs, reflective evaluations, and iterative planning meetings to ensure relevance and responsiveness.

2.2 Coding

The second methodological component involved a structured qualitative analysis of documentation and outputs from each RWL. Using a combination of deductive coding (informed by the Tandem Framework's principles and phases) and inductive coding (to capture emerging themes), we assessed Tandem's guiding questions categorized under sub-code themes, and the "good principles" of co-production, providing a categorisation scheme to evaluate successes and challenges of co-production in RWLs.

Tandem Element	MEL Element ¹	Theme	Sub-code	Impact code ²	
Scope, review identify and engage	Context-based	Risks, vulnerability and challenges (climate and non-climate)	Natural hazards/disaster risks	Holistic overview of risks and vulnerabilities.	
			Climate and disaster risks		
			Non-climate/disaster risks		
			Socio-economic vulnerabilities		
		Impacts	Natural hazards/disasters	Holistic overview of impacts.	
			Environmental impacts		
			Climate and disaster impacts		
			Non-climate/disaster impacts		
	Pluralistic	Identified and engaged relevant actors and champions	Stakeholders relating to climate/risk information and data	Increased awareness and understanding of knowledge and stakeholder landscape.	
			Stakeholders involved in decision-making process		
			Stakeholders vulnerable/at risk		
			Knowledge systems engaged with	Improved communication (e.g. trust, dialogue, co-production, language).	
Methods of engagement used					
Co-explore	Goal-oriented	Co-explore challenges and goals	Socio-economic challenges (e.g. income, education)	Creating shared understanding - consensus building around priorities, where it was absent previously, for example.	
			Decision-making challenges (e.g. representation, responsibilities, data)		
			Communication challenges (e.g. language, terminology, channels)		
			Adaptation challenges (e.g. climate, social, economic, political, environmental)		
		Co-explore governance context	Windows of opportunity	Increased understand of governance levers of change.	
			Institutional capacity/arrangements		
			Existing plans, policies, and projects		
			Governance mechanism		
		Co-explore information needs	Appropriate format	Increased awareness and understanding of challenges, risks, and impacts faced through enhanced understanding of the use and limits of data/models.	
			Relevant language		
			Accessible terminology		
			Capacity to articulate needs		
			Information channel		
		Co-design solutions	Co-explore and identify solutions	Appropriate scales (relevant to temporal and spatial scales of decision)	Solutions that provide increased resilience to climate and disaster risk.
				Relevant to decision context	
Salience (priority need)					
			Credibility (trusted)		

Table 1: The combination of Tandem codes applied.

2.2.1 Development of the codebook

2.2.1.1 MEL-Based Deductive Coding

The first set of deductive codes draws on the Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (MEL) strategy outlined in Deliverable 1.2 (Capacity Development Strategy for DIRECTED). This includes the integration of the “good principles” for knowledge co-production proposed by Norström et al. (2020), and the structured assessment of Tandem’s guiding questions. Each guiding question was assigned a corresponding code, forming a core structure for analysis. In cases of thematic overlap or similar questions, duplicate or related codes were created to ensure comprehensive coverage.

2.2.1.2 Inductive Coding

Inductive codes were developed during the review process to capture new themes, concepts, and implementation challenges that were not addressed in the original Tandem framework. These emergent codes are particularly useful for identifying gaps in knowledge co-production practice, evolving stakeholder needs, and barriers in DRM and CCA settings.

2.2.1.3 Framework Structure

The coding framework consists of the following key elements:

- **Code Groups and Sub-Groups:** Organized into thematic areas and Tandem phases, allowing for structured comparison across different RWLs.
- **Primary Codes:** Grouped into:
 - Risk Governance (e.g., Policy and Planning, Decision-Making)
 - Knowledge Co-Production (e.g., Stakeholder Engagement, Citizen Involvement)
 - Data and Models (e.g., Data Interoperability, Uncertainty)
 - Hazards and Climate Change (e.g., Floods, Droughts)
 - Vulnerability (e.g., Economic, Social, Physical Vulnerabilities)
 - Tandem Elements: Phases 1a–3c, with sub-codes reflecting guiding questions
 - Cross-Cutting Themes: MEL, Communication, Monitoring (e.g., confidence, relationships)
- **Sub-Codes:** Specific to each group or Tandem element, these allow for granular analysis (e.g., “Data Governance” under Data and Models).
- **Co-occurrence:** Used to explore thematic relationships and overlaps between codes. This helped:

- Identify interactions between hazards, governance, and co-production
- Analyze synergies or redundancies within Tandem questions
- Link guiding questions to emergent inductive codes (e.g., highlighting new implementation needs)
- **Tags:** Ungrouped codes used for filtering thematic issues like “Climate Change,” “Equity,” or “Uncertainty.” These improve specificity in retrieval and help identify topics that span multiple categories.

2.2.1.4 Coding of RWL Outputs

All relevant RWL documents, including workshop materials, lab papers, transcripts, and debrief notes, were imported into Atlas.ti and coded using the developed framework. Coding followed an iterative process to ensure the integration of both predefined and emergent codes.

2.2.2 Coding framework implementation

The following steps were taken:

- **Code Creation:** All framework codes and sub-codes were created within Atlas.ti.
- **Data Segment Coding:** Text segments were highlighted and assigned codes (e.g., “Communication” + “Flood” when issues with coordination during floods were mentioned).
- **Co-occurrence Mapping:** Relationships between commonly co-occurring codes (e.g., “Physical Vulnerability” + “Flood”) were visualized and documented.
- **Tagging:** Topic-specific tags (e.g., “Climate Adaptation”) were applied to relevant segments.
- **New Code Development:** New sub-codes were added where needed. For example, “Missing Stakeholders” was created under Phase 1c to capture overlooked groups.

These codes were then grouped and analyzed under the Tandem refinement priorities identified in ‘M16 Tandem Iteratively Applied’ to further identify gaps and opportunities for Tandem refinement.

- **Integration of DRR and CCA**
- **Multi-hazard and legacy risk management approach**
- **Citizen engagement**
- **Communicating uncertainty**

- **Data interoperability**
- **Capacity development**
- **Monitoring, evaluation, and learning**

3. Findings

This section will explore the findings from the DIRECTED document coding and the Capacity Needs Assessment and provide recommendations for the ongoing capacity development work in DIRECTED and Tandem updates, as well as the subsequent Capacity Development Modules.

3.1 Capacity Needs Assessment

This section presents the results of the Capacity Needs Assessment conducted with RWL hosts at the end of 2024, capturing both the situation prior to DIRECTED and the progress made during the first two years. Initial needs were identified through iterative scoping consultations with individual labs to understand their goals, challenges, and development priorities. A more formal assessment was introduced only later in the project, as self-assessment can be difficult when participants are unfamiliar with certain concepts. Capacities are often easier to recognize and evaluate upon reflection, after gaining experience and practice, rather than at the outset. To address this, capacity development training was first provided in response to the scoping consultations, giving labs the opportunity to build their understanding before undertaking a structured assessment. However, this assessment yielded limited responses, with only six lab hosts completing the form, and RWL 2 (Emilia-Romagna) opting to respond collectively. Furthermore, structured monitoring through the capacity needs assessment form has also been constrained by staff turnover. At this stage, we combined insights from the scoping consultations, the co-design of lab engagements, and the debriefs with the findings from this Capacity Needs Assessment.

3.1.1 Design

When exploring 'Design' as a skill for co-production, most RWL hosts described "design thinking" in their RWL context as a way to creatively engage and exchange with stakeholders, develop discussion techniques, consider multiple perspectives, and actively involve users in developing data, insights, digital tools, and models. Some answers emphasized design thinking's role in mapping complex problems, understanding stakeholder interactions, and identifying solutions tailored to stakeholder needs.

Figure 1: Capacity Needs Assessment Design Skills Results.

As demonstrated in [Figure 1](#), before DIRECTED, most respondents reported limited to some experience with design processes and creative methods. Uses were often occasional or project-specific rather than embedded in their ways of working, focusing on stakeholder engagement, workshop facilitation, or iterative problem-solving.

RWL hosts generally scored the value of design thinking for their day-to-day work as slightly to quite valuable. Those with more exposure recognized its potential to improve stakeholder engagement, co-production, and problem-solving, while a few still expressed some doubts about its applicability. In the RWL context, design processes and creative methods were mostly rated as quite valuable, particularly for engaging stakeholders, understanding complex problems, and developing collaborative solutions.

Regarding skills and confidence, most participants rated their ability to design knowledge co-production processes and utilize design thinking as moderate, indicating some confidence but room for growth. A small number reported low confidence, especially when applying design thinking systematically. DIRECTED was reported to have moderately improved skills across participants, with some indicating only slight improvements, reflecting the early stage of experience and the need for continued practice and application.

Ongoing support needs identified by lab hosts included:

- Further practical guidance and training in structured design processes.
- Opportunities to apply creative methods systematically in RWL activities.

- Sharing experiences and best practices from other RWLs to build confidence in using design thinking effectively.

3.1.2 Research

When exploring ‘Research’ as a skill for co-production, most RWL hosts reported having varied research experience before DIRECTED. Some regularly led and designed research projects, including European projects, supervision of student theses, and over 20 years of academic research using disciplinary, interdisciplinary, and transdisciplinary methods. Several participants had primarily participated in or supported research, often through university studies, PhD work, or research assistant roles.

Figure 2: Capacity Needs Assessment Research Skills Results.

As demonstrated in [Figure 2](#), RWL hosts consistently rated qualitative methods, such as interviews, surveys, and focus groups, as ‘quite’ to ‘extremely’ valuable for understanding stakeholders’ needs. Despite recognizing the importance of these methods, most participants felt only moderately confident in enabling, leading, or applying qualitative research independently. Similarly, their ability to lead surveys, interviews, or focus group discussions, as well as manage and collect data, was generally rated moderate, indicating room for growth. Confidence in monitoring, evaluating, and learning from knowledge co-production processes was somewhat higher, with most rating themselves moderate and a few high.

DIRECTED has contributed to moderate improvement in research skills across participants. Most respondents reported that their abilities to conduct qualitative research, link research to stakeholder engagement, and manage research outputs had strengthened to a moderate

extent. Some participants noted only slight improvements, highlighting that further skill development is still required.

Ongoing support needs identified by lab hosts included:

- Clarifying the connection between RWL activities and research objectives.
- Practical guidance on applying qualitative methods effectively with stakeholders.
- Strengthening data management skills, including systematic collection and organization of transcripts, workshop outcomes, and survey results.
- Improved integration of monitoring, evaluation, and learning practices to capture lessons from co-production.
- Continued exchange of experiences with other RWLs and DIRECTED colleagues to enhance method application and research practices.

3.1.3 Facilitation

When exploring 'Facilitation' as a skill for co-production, most RWL hosts rated themselves as low to moderate in confidence to facilitate co-production workshops before DIRECTED. Several individuals felt "somewhat confident" but acknowledged clear room for growth, while a few reported low confidence, feeling unsure of their abilities. Only one participant indicated 'high confidence' before DIRECTED. Similarly, RWL hosts generally rated 'low' to 'moderate' in facilitating creative/interactive methods before DIRECTED. Many participants highlighted limited prior experience, with some explicitly stating 'very low' confidence in using such methods.

Figure 3: Capacity Needs Assessment Facilitation Skills Results.

However, as demonstrated in [Figure 3](#), ratings improved significantly, ranging from ‘moderate’ to ‘high’ in current confidence to facilitate co-production workshops. RWL hosts expressed increased assurance in their ability to facilitate knowledge co-production. They consistently rated their listening skills ‘high’ to ‘very high’, suggesting strong capacity in empathetic engagement and attentiveness to participants. RWL hosts were a little less confident in facilitating discussions, rating ‘moderate’ to ‘high’. In contrast, responses to facilitating conflict management were more mixed: from ‘low’ to ‘moderate’ for some, to ‘very high’ for others.

When asked about DIRECTED’s Contribution to Capacity Building, most respondents indicated that DIRECTED has improved their skills to a ‘large extent’, enabling them to better connect risk/climate data with stakeholder requirements. In regard to facilitating creative and interactive activities, improvement was reported across all responses. Some noted significant skill gains - for example, in RWL 4 (Rhine-Erft), the host initially reported having low confidence in leading co-production workshops and very limited ability in facilitating creative or interactive methods. One of the primary challenges in RWL 4 (Rhine-Erft) had been “participant reluctance and vague contributions”, which made knowledge co-production difficult. Through DIRECTED, however, the host’s confidence and skills grew substantially; she now ranks her ability in facilitation and interactive methods as high, reflecting that her skills have improved ‘to a large extent’. Her openness to experimenting with new approaches, coupled with a sensitivity to participants’ perceptions, enabled the gradual introduction of different facilitation techniques without overwhelming participants with methods they might have considered too creative, unconventional or “silly” in a formal setting. By aligning methods with participant perceptions and capacities, DIRECTED enabled the RWL 4 (Rhine-Erft) host to adopt new approaches without risking disengagement, trust or credibility, thereby strengthening both her individual capacity and the overall effectiveness of the RWL.

Other RWL hosts described moderate improvement, with room for growth. This will be supported by building on previous activities and addressing specific needs identified by RWL hosts, including:

- Assistance in preparation of meetings and method selection for RWL activities.
- Continued collaboration and exchange with DIRECTED colleagues, especially WP 4, in planning future workshops.
- Practical guidance and shared experiences on methods to apply within RWLs.
- Some participants expressed uncertainty about future needs, while others suggested reassessment after more time working with stakeholders.

3.1.4 Collaboration

When exploring ‘Collaboration’ as a capacity for co-production, most RWL hosts rated their ability to build trust and relationships between stakeholders as ‘moderate’ to ‘very high’ prior to DIRECTED, but still reported additional improvements in their capacity as a result of DIRECTED’s contribution. Similarly, as demonstrated in [Figure 4](#), lab hosts generally rated their ability to create open and safe spaces for stakeholder discussions as ‘moderate’ to ‘very high’.

Figure 4: Capacity Needs Assessment Collaborative Capacity Results.

RWL hosts highlighted a variety of ways in which DIRECTED supported collaboration and knowledge co-production in their RWLs. The project provided inspiration from other RWLs and offered suggestions for methods, as well as support in preparing and implementing activities. It also proposed specific activities and guided questions for stakeholder engagement exercises, helping hosts to design meaningful interactions. In addition, DIRECTED facilitated a platform for exchange between key actors in DRM and CCA, creating opportunities to build a broader understanding of different stakeholder approaches, perspectives, and goals. By offering a framework for joint learning, the project helped accelerate common understanding and strengthened partnerships for co-production. Participants also gained clarity on where they could best contribute to DIRECTED and to their own RWLs, with direct support from WP 3 and WP 4 partners in planning and conducting knowledge co-production workshops, as well as in organizing internal sessions for presentations and Q&A. This offers great insight into the existing exercises to continue in

DIRECTED further played a role in promoting collaboration between DRM and CCA. It brought together diverse stakeholder groups to foster mutual understanding of goals and methods, and it encouraged cross-sector dialogue and exploration of collaborative

opportunities. Structured exercises were provided to highlight overlaps and complementary perspectives between DRM and CCA actors, helping to build bridges between communities that do not always work together directly.

Despite these efforts, RWL hosts identified several challenges to enabling collaboration and knowledge co-production. Some participants showed reluctance or made unspecific statements, which limited their engagement in activities. It was also difficult at times to engage both institutional and non-institutional stakeholders, and to convince stakeholders to think beyond their own perspectives and consider alternative viewpoints. Cultural passivity or lack of active participation further hindered discussions in some cases. Organizational complexity also created challenges, as in Denmark, where the absence of coordination mechanism for CCA/ DRM across the Roskilde Fjord meant that coordination between multiple municipalities and emergency services required additional effort. Finally, personnel changes within RWL teams, especially in the Capital Region of Denmark RWL slowed down trust-building processes, making it necessary to re-establish relationships with stakeholders repeatedly.

Ongoing support needs identified by RWL hosts included:

- Better understanding of processes, structures, roles, responsibilities, and capabilities to identify collaboration opportunities.
- Continued guidance on knowledge co-production methods and strategies.
- Approaches to build common awareness of the importance of adapting to climate change.
- Support in translating scientific results into practical, common language for stakeholders.

3.1.5 Systems Thinking

When exploring ‘Systems Thinking’ as a capacity for co-production, most RWL hosts described “systems thinking” in their RWL context as the ability to view challenges holistically, understand interconnections between hazards, risks, and climate change, and consider multiple stakeholder perspectives to reach shared goals, including its importance for cross-cutting collaboration across municipalities, emergency services, and other key actors. Several participants noted that systems thinking requires working in parallel with many stakeholders and considering multiple aspects of climate change simultaneously. However, some defined it as integrating different tools, data, and scenarios, suggesting a mis-interpretation for the purpose of Tandem.

Figure 5: Capacity Needs Assessment Systems Thinking Capacity Results.

Before DIRECTED, as demonstrated in [Figure 5](#), most RWL hosts reported ‘limited’ or ‘occasional’ use of systems thinking. A few had applied it in certain projects or tasks, while others had used it ‘regularly’ as part of their work. The approach was often unstructured, and respondents noted that it was applied inconsistently across projects.

RWL hosts rated the value of systems thinking for their day-to-day work from ‘quite’ to ‘extremely valuable’, with most emphasizing its essential role in understanding complex risks and supporting decision-making. Skills in utilizing systems thinking in daily work were rated ‘moderate’ to ‘high’. Competence in understanding complexity and interconnectedness between disaster risk and climate change was also generally rated ‘moderate’ to ‘high’, while the ability to communicate complexity was slightly lower for some participants. Skills in conducting integrated risk assessments and developing or using risk scenarios in workshops ranged from ‘moderate’ to ‘very high’, depending on prior experience.

DIRECTED was reported to have ‘moderately’ to ‘largely’ improved systems thinking skills for most. Within RWL 2 (Emilia-Romagna) the hosts reported that DIRECTED had improved their capacity in systems thinking by a ‘large extent’. Improvements included better recognition of connections between disciplines, hazards, risks, and climate change, and enhanced confidence in applying systems thinking to RWL activities and scenario development. A few hosts reported only slight improvements, often reflecting already high prior experience or regular application of systems thinking principles.

Ongoing support needs identified by RWL hosts included:

- Guidance on appropriate methods and questions to ask to integrate systems thinking effectively.
- Tools and ideas to better evaluate cascading impacts, uncertainty, and interactions across risks and climate change.
- Support in modelling and scenario development that incorporates climate change projections.
- Advice on translating systems thinking into actionable approaches within risk management processes.

3.1.6 Reflexivity

When exploring ‘Reflexivity’ as a capacity for co-production, lab hosts identified key attributes such as critical thinking, self-awareness, empathy, open-mindedness, and the ability to accept or process criticism. Additional attributes mentioned included good observation, attention to detail, and analytical ability, all contributing to the capacity to critically assess one’s own actions, assumptions, and decisions.

Figure 6: Capacity Needs Assessment Reflexive Capacity Results.

As demonstrated in [Figure 6](#), respondents reported that they engage in reflection ‘regularly’, although some noted that reflection occurs less consistently under certain conditions, such as time pressure, emergencies, group settings with unfamiliar participants, or when discussing new topics they are less familiar with.

Reflective capacity was widely regarded as ‘extremely valuable’ or ‘quite valuable’ in both professional and personal contexts. Most lab hosts expressed ‘high confidence’ in their ability to critically reflect, though a few rated themselves only ‘moderately confident’, indicating room for growth.

DIRECTED’s contribution to enhancing reflexive capacity was reported as small to moderate for most participants, with a few noting large improvements. Some hosts highlighted the use of debriefings in small groups, self-reflection sheets, design thinking methods, and self-reflection questionnaires as helpful tools or frameworks for supporting reflective practice. However, others indicated that they lacked sufficient structured resources or were unsure how to systematically improve their reflective practices. A concrete example of reflexivity arose from the social vulnerability maps, developed by University College Cork, using available census data. These maps were used during an exercise at the European Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA) Conference (June 2025, Rimini) and sparked strong interest from the Civil Protection Officers. The exercise revealed overlooked vulnerabilities, for example, the high number of elderly homes in the Northern areas, which was not evident in the census data. This underscored the importance of continued reflexivity, asking who is (and is not) represented in the data, whose voices shape the conversation, and whose needs are prioritized in planning. Such questioning moves reflexivity beyond a technical exercise to a critical practice that challenges assumptions, surfaces blind spots, and prompts inclusive responses. As a result, local actors initiated the collection of more detailed data from the Municipality of Rimini, to update the Social Vulnerability Index and then include it in the Data Fabric as an additional source of information for civil protection planning and/or in operations.

Despite such progress, several challenges to reflexivity were noted. These were commonly linked to time constraints and high-pressure situations, such as stressful or emergency contexts. RWL hosts discussed that often they were forced into immediate problem-solving, especially when topics required rapid decision-making without prior preparation, leaving little space for deeper consideration and critical self-awareness. Additionally, group settings also posed difficulties, particularly when participants felt insecure or unfamiliar with others, making them less inclined to share openly.

Ongoing support needs identified by lab hosts included:

- Practical frameworks or structured tools for reflection that can be applied consistently.
- Methods to integrate reflexive practices into daily work routines, even under pressure.
- Guidance on combining reflective practices with collaborative and creative processes.

3.1.7 Creativity

When exploring ‘creativity’ as a capacity for co-production, RWL hosts identified attributes such as imagination, open-mindedness, problem-solving, experimentation, and the ability to think “out of the box”. Several respondents also highlighted the importance of motivation, optimism, courage, and the willingness to explore new perspectives, particularly in understanding stakeholders’ needs.

Figure 7: Capacity Needs Assessment Creative Capacity Results.

Hosts reported engaging in creative thinking and problem-solving from ‘occasionally’, regularly to ‘always’. Most rated creative capacity as ‘quite’ to ‘extremely’ valuable, however, confidence in generating innovative ideas varied: most felt ‘highly confident’, a few were ‘moderately confident’, and a small number reported ‘low confidence’, reflecting differing experience levels and comfort with creative approaches.

The biggest barriers to expressing or developing creativity centered around perceived structural barriers such as limited support or guidance from organizations, including time and resource constraints and rigid processes. Hosts also noted fear of failure or lack of confidence as a barrier. However, participants reported nurturing creativity, using practices such as brainstorming and mind-mapping, reflecting on past decisions and their outcomes, engaging in creative hobbies, and actively putting themselves in the shoes of other stakeholders to explore alternative perspectives.

DIRECTED was reported to have moderately to largely enhanced creative capacity for most respondents, though some noted only slight improvement and one reported no contribution. Several hosts highlighted the value of learning new methods and structured approaches, although some noted that creative thinking often comes naturally, with the main challenges being external constraints, such as concerns over how the method might be perceived by colleagues. In RWL 3 (Zala), the host reflected that DIRECTED had increased their creative capacity to a “large extent.” Working with the WP 4 team, the host co-designed a series of workshops that introduced creative and interactive activities previously unfamiliar to both the host and participants. One example was a play-based introduction exercise, where participants created something to express what “climate resilient West Balaton” meant to them. This activity helped break down hierarchies and fostered an open environment for sharing experiences. Participant feedback further indicated that they enjoyed the groupwork as a new and effective way of exchanging knowledge.

Ongoing support needs identified by lab hosts included:

- More guidance on tools and frameworks to systematically support creative practices.
- Examples or structured approaches for integrating creativity into RWL activities.
- Opportunities to experiment safely and overcome organizational constraints that limit creative thinking.

Recommendations:

Across all skills and capacities, RWL hosts emphasized the value of DIRECTED’s ongoing guidance on practical frameworks, methods, and questions to use with stakeholders. They expressed a clear need for this support to continue, along with additional guidance on how to facilitate these approaches with lab participants. This highlights opportunities for refining the Tandem process and introducing exercises to strengthen the use of guiding questions in practice.

In addition, RWL hosts noted a strong desire for support in technical areas such as modelling, scenario development, and governance tools to better address uncertainty. This feedback is particularly valuable for informing the application of the Risk-Tandem Framework (see Deliverable 3.2) and the e-Learning resources (Deliverable 6.4, available in June 2026).

3.2 Evaluating the co-production process

The results of the MEL-based deductive coding that informed the capacity development modules are presented in this section. Insights from the coding will aid us in understanding the iterative application of Tandem within the RWLs and where there are strengths to be carried forward and opportunities for further development. The themes and insights generated from this coding are also informing the wider learning programs being developed for the DIRECTED e-Learning Platform focused on supporting integrated DRM and CCA based RWL experiences, processes and outputs.

3.2.1 Integration of DRR and CCA

Integration of DRR and CCA was predominantly evident in Phase 1 deductive and inductive coding. However, Phase 2 deductive codes such as ‘Information used for Decision Making’ and ‘Governance strategy’ also explored the need for integration of DRR and CCA - these will be explored further in [3.2.2 Multi-hazard and legacy risk management approach](#) and [3.2.5 Capacity development](#).

Deductive coding revealed a strong weighting toward ‘hazards’ and ‘climate’ (26 codes to climate and 81 to hazards), as well as significant attention to physical vulnerability (40 codes). Climate change was consistently referred to as a driver of more frequent and intense hazards, increasing exposure and therefore risk. ‘Hazards’ explored how natural hazards interact with socio-economic systems. While economical areas were recognized as vulnerable to hazard impacts, there was comparatively less emphasis on biodiversity impacts, suggesting an imbalance in attention between economic and ecological vulnerabilities.

Across the analysis, several emergent codes extended the scope of the original Tandem guiding questions, with ‘CCA’, ‘DRM’, and ‘infrastructure’ emerging as with the highest frequency. The inductive code ‘CCA’ (25 references) emphasized the need for flexible solutions that can adapt to multiple pathways and scenarios. It frequently co-occurred with codes: ‘goals’, ‘policy and planning’, ‘DRM’, ‘ideas’, and ‘existing interventions’. The inductive code ‘DRM’ (45 references) was more frequently cited and strongly tied to codes: ‘goals’, ‘challenges’, ‘existing interventions’; and emergent codes: ‘preparedness’ and ‘disaster response’. The inductive code ‘infrastructure’ (29 references) cut across both DRM and CCA, pointing to vulnerabilities in physical structures as potential for risk as well as an area for intervention.

The inductive code 'preparedness' (23 references) overlapped with DRM but focused on proactive measures and risk governance, connecting to 'risk governance challenges', 'DRM', 'ideas', 'goals', and 'ways of working'.

Other inductive codes captured a wide spectrum of themes, ranging from DRM-related issues such as 'Failure of Equipment' and 'Recovery', to adaptation measures including 'Mitigation' and 'Retreat'. The inductive code 'Cultural Shift' highlighted the recognition that addressing risk requires more than technical solutions; it calls for a shift toward long-term thinking and proactive engagement with uncertainty. Similarly, the code 'Finance' reflected the importance of sustainable financing models, particularly those that can support the generation of additional data and resources to enable stronger integration and implementation of DRR and CCA.

Recommendations:

In order to better understand and facilitate the integration of DRM and CCA it is important that the Tandem process (supported by Risk-Tandem) explicitly probes the connections between hazards, exposure and vulnerability to understand sources of risk. While it already tries to identify underlying and multiple sources of vulnerability as well as the drivers that might exacerbate it or result in maladaptation, methods to explore this can be challenging. This includes understanding the interactions between natural phenomena and urban development (for example, how urban expansion contributes to, and drives wildfire risks), behaviors and current activities, and how these impact vulnerability and exposure. For example, the construction of lightweight structures on the beach that can be picked up by wind gusts during storms, or the excessive privatization of beaches that leads to difficulties in establishing a shared approach to risk management and adaptation.

Exercises should explore how infrastructure is both affected by hazards and how it contributes to cascading impacts during crises. Additionally, deductive coding showed that economic areas were frequently highlighted as vulnerable, while biodiversity impacts received far less attention. Future Tandem iterations should prompt participants to consider both economic and ecological vulnerabilities, and how these interact under climate change. This could form the basis of broader risk-mapping questions, linking physical vulnerabilities to socio-economic and ecological systems. The mapping of systems will enable a coordinated DRR and CCA approach with explicit tagging of challenges, goals and ideas. New guiding questions should be accompanied by processes/exercises to guide Tandem users to connect across systems and understand drivers of risk to ensure that DRM plans align with CCA priorities, and that multi-hazard approaches are embedded across governance levels, sectors, and timescales.

3.2.2 Multi-hazard and legacy risk management approach

The inductive code 'Ways of Working' was one of the most prominent themes, referenced 91 times, and reflected both practical methods and systemic challenges in managing risk. It frequently co-occurred with 'ideas' (8 references), where mapping, preparedness drills, practical exercises, futures thinking, and scenario-based simulations were highlighted as tools to engage stakeholders. Links with 'challenges' (14 references) discussed fragmented systems and the lack of consistent management exercises, while overlaps with 'goals' (11 references) emphasized aspirations for better resource allocation, large-scale multi-stakeholder workshops, proactive knowledge exchange, and deeper local engagement. 'Collaboration and coordination' (9 references) were also central, re-iterating the missing cross-boundary cooperation. Overall, the code highlighted the need to strengthen everyday practices, embed regular drills, and build collaborative frameworks that address risks across sectors and scales - this theme is also explored in [Section 3.2.5 Capacity development](#). Importantly, the discussions reflected the desire for a strengthened multi-hazard risk management approach.

The deductive code 'Maladaptation Risks' (4 references), though infrequently cited, highlighted the unintended negative consequences of well-intentioned interventions. Discussions mainly came from RWL 3 in the Zala Region, exploring government-provided agricultural incentives, where farmers are compensated for crop losses. While these measures aim to reduce economic risk, they can inadvertently encourage cultivation across all available land to increase compensation amounts, including environmentally sensitive areas, resulting in negative environmental impacts. This finding underscores the importance of carefully designing policies and interventions to avoid creating new vulnerabilities while addressing existing risks, closely linking to broader themes of climate adaptation, long-term planning, and sustainable land management.

The emergent code 'Risk Knowledge' (9 references) co-occurred with 'goals' (4 references), reflecting the desire and need to build risk knowledge. Discussions highlighted the role of knowledge exchange among practitioners, use of tools such as action cards to communicate hazards and appropriate responses, and the need to enhance citizens' understanding of risks. Several emergent codes provided more detailed areas of focus and pointed to opportunities for refining future Tandem questions and exercises. These included governance themes such as 'Existing Funding', 'Formalisation of Stakeholders', 'Lack of Political Awareness', 'Political Priority', 'Risk Communication Channels', 'Invest' and 'Roles and Responsibility'. These underscore the need to clarify accountability, secure resources, and strengthen political will for adaptation and risk management. Alongside these institutional concerns, 'Tourism' (highlighting risk-informed development and sector-specific vulnerabilities), and 'Nature-Based Solutions' (reinforcing the importance of green

infrastructure and ecological approaches) emerged. Finally, the code 'Speculative Futures' reflected a more forward-looking approach, reflective of the exercises and dialogue around long-term uncertainties, alternative scenarios, and transition pathways.

Recommendations:

Given the limited reference to the code 'Maladaptation Risks', Tandem should introduce structured processes for systematically exploring maladaptation and multi-risk interactions. This builds on the existing guiding question: "Are multiple risks (climate and non-climate) being considered, and is there potential for maladaptation, compound, or cascading effects across departments, sectors, or locations?", but goes further by formalizing and expanding what has already been piloted in risk mapping exercises in the Rhein-Erft RWL tabletop exercise for example.

Addressing maladaptation requires recognizing that climate change, biodiversity loss, and poverty are wicked problems: ill-defined, interdependent, and spanning multiple scales (Rittel & Webber, 1973; Buchanan, 1995; Coyne, 2005). Traditional design approaches risk oversimplification and "pseudo solutions" (Irwin, 2018). By applying systems thinking and acknowledging the presence of multiple complex adaptive systems (CAS) (Zivkovic, 2018), Tandem can guide toward processes that strengthen the learning capacity and adaptive resilience of real-world labs. This reflects what Wallace (2021) describes as the "real innovation" of the CAS approach (Borkar et al., 2020; Hassan, 2014; Zivkovic, 2018).

This is particularly relevant given emergent thematic codes such as tourism and nature-based solutions, which underline that DIRECTED operates across multiple systems and contexts. Here, systems mapping frameworks such as Wallace's Multi-Layer Perspective mapping (2021) could be used to connect risk management with broader sustainability transitions, for example, aligning flood resilience with ecological restoration, risk-informed tourism, or climate-sensitive urban planning. This would support cultural and institutional shifts from reactive crisis management to anticipatory, long-term, and transformative resilience building.

To strengthen this future orientation, Tandem should integrate futures thinking and long-term pathways into its exercises, through exercises such as multi-layer perspective mapping. Building on the emergent code 'Speculative Futures', this would enable stakeholders to explore long-term uncertainties, alternative adaptation pathways, and transition scenarios, while recognizing how the historical context, such as land-use decisions shape present and future vulnerabilities. Transition Design (Irwin, 2015; Norman & Stappers, 2016) offers useful strategies here, combining systems thinking, participatory methods, and long-term visions to create "ecologies of interventions" (Kossof et al., 2015; Manzini, 2015).

3.2.3 Citizen engagement

Citizen engagement was only marginally reflected in the coding, appearing under deductive codes 'Missing Stakeholders' (2 references) and 'Unequal or Missing Representation' (4 references). Even here, discussions remained limited, with few concrete examples of how to effectively involve citizens or ensure equitable participation in governance or planning. The emphasis was largely on acknowledging absence rather than exploring mechanisms for inclusion.

Additionally, codes that explored power such as 'Stakeholder power' and 'Working with power imbalance' received limited reference (5 references and 6 references). Within these references there was some discussion of citizen engagement, through conversations around who holds power to decide policy direction (e.g. European Commission, insurers, local communities) and how support can be gained from the top and from the bottom, to align interests.

In contrast, 'Public Risk Communication Issues' was a highly referenced deductive code, with 30 references, and reflected a more developed discussion. This theme overlapped with 'Ideas' (7 references), which included suggestions such as producing instructional videos, creating common communication platforms, and even framing communication itself as a form of risk mitigation. It also connected with 'Communication Responsibilities' (5 references), where RWL 1 (The Capital Region of Denmark) participants noted that municipalities often operated in and with separate systems, creating fragmentation and uncertainty over what constituted effective communication.

The prominence of risk communication, compared with the marginal focus on direct citizen engagement, suggests that while systems for informing the public are recognized as critical, the active involvement of citizens in decision-making and preparedness planning remains underdeveloped. Strengthening communication channels and clarifying responsibilities across governance levels were seen as central to building public awareness, preparedness, and trust. However, the limited coding around representation highlights a critical gap in the RWLs related to: meaningful engagement, equitable inclusion, and the integration of local voices into governance processes.

Recommendations:

The gap between meaningful citizen engagement and the emphasis on communication represents a key opportunity for future Tandem development. This could be advanced through both co-designed exercises and new Tandem questions that probe how citizen knowledge can be harnessed, how participation can be incentivized, and how representation can be embedded into risk governance and climate adaptation strategies. In addition, Tandem has provided practical guidance on the process of setting up a transdisciplinary lab, to ensure involvement of citizens, within the Tandem Overview and Foundation Modules.

3.2.4 Communicating uncertainty and Data interoperability

The coding revealed a strong link between data interoperability and the communication of uncertainty. Participants repeatedly attributed difficulties in conveying uncertainty to the lack of interoperable data. The code ‘Data Interoperability’ (25 references) had the highest co-occurrence with ‘Goal’, ‘User Needs’, and ‘Data Sharing’ repeatedly referencing the need for a central place to gain an “overview of different data”, and enable the “alignment of maps and models”, and “link real time groundwater levels and precipitation”.

This was further illustrated by the deductive code ‘Models’ (58 references), one of the most prominent codes relating to communicating uncertainty, with discussions centered on the demand for more precise, reliable, and integrated modelling approaches. Participants highlighted the need for: more accurate forecasts, especially for coupled and cascading events; improved modelling of infrastructure capacities (e.g., pumps, flood barriers); enhanced integration of complex datasets, including sensor data; and increased accessibility of model outputs to end users. The code ‘Time Horizons of Information’ (11 references) reflected a mismatch over which time horizons should guide be prioritized. While DRM actors typically work with 72-hour forecasts, climate adaptation planning requires much longer-term perspectives and thus a common goal is key. Challenges also emerged around the timeliness of sensor data, with lags undermining its usefulness for sudden-onset events.

The code ‘Data Limitations’ (33 references) reinforced these barriers. Focussing on: data uncertainty and inconsistency between tools; restrictions from data protection laws (GDPR); insufficient precision in forecasting and measuring tools. Participants stressed the need to overcome these limitations through improved precision, expanded measurement, and more open, shared datasets. Complementing this, the inductive code ‘Data Sources and Collection’ (27 references) reflected calls for stronger regional monitoring networks and more localized data collection, including additional measuring points, wave buoys, tide gauges, monitoring stations, webcams, and oceanographic forecasts.

The co-occurring code ‘User Needs’ (13 references) again reinforced the connection between data interoperability and communicating uncertainty, with calls for models that not only advance technical accuracy but also respond directly to the requirements of practitioners, decision-makers, and citizens. Goals included “better models” and “more accurate forecasts,” while challenges related to data complexity and difficulties in operationalizing model outputs.

The code ‘Existing Interventions’ (10 references) and ‘Leveraging existing work and/or partnerships’ (25 references) noted that a variety of models, tools, and databases are already in place. However, the related code ‘Data Credibility’ (14 references) highlighted persistent concerns about uncertainty, lack of precision, and inconsistency between different

tools. This suggests that while the technical infrastructure exists, credibility and ability to make decisions based on the data available are barriers. This was further enforced by the code 'Data Visualization' (46 references), which revealed a strong demand for tools that make complex information more interpretable and actionable ([Section 5.3](#)). Closely linked codes, 'Data Sharing', 'Tailoring Communication', and 'User Information Formats', stressed that communication formats must be audience-specific; this included technical outputs for practitioners, but also clear, simplified visuals and targeted campaigns for citizens. The overarching goal was to democratize data access, with references to open datasets, unified databases, integration of private monitoring data, and direct citizen communication channels.

Recommendations:

The coding highlights a gap in understanding what models and data are available and can address, leading to repeated requests for “better data” as a means of reducing uncertainty. While improved data can help, it is equally important to communicate the inherent limitations of models and datasets. Doing so will help stakeholders better grasp the unavoidable aspects of uncertainty, and limitations of models to meet governance and communication needs, encouraging innovation to address these gaps. This is explored further in D4.2. To strengthen this, Tandem should establish processes that:

- support shared understanding and open discussion of data and model limitations.
- identify and address skills gaps in data interpretation among stakeholders.
- foster innovation around existing gaps, including methods for working with uncertainty.

3.2.5 Capacity development

The code 'Collaboration / Coordination' was highly referenced (83 references), emerging both as a challenge and a goal, and closely tied to governance strategy. Participants consistently emphasized that effective prevention and long term adaptation planning requires action at every level, from local to national, and coordination across multiple sectors. This included developing cross-sectoral action plans, fostering interdisciplinary alliances, and strengthening dialogue about future responsibilities. Collaboration was also linked to enhancing technical and institutional capacities. A strong future-oriented dimension was evident through its co-occurrence with 'goals', highlighting the need to align standards, clarify responsibilities, and embed foresight into governance strategies.

Capacity-building emerged as a critical enabler of collaboration. The deductive code 'Skills and Capacities for Risk Governance' and inductive codes 'Simulation' and 'Training' underscored the demand for technical capacity development, particularly through training in regional warning systems and for specific roles such as beach managers. The inductive code 'Knowledge Sharing' reinforced this, pointing to aspirations for exchange both within organizations and across sectors, especially between DRM and CCA professionals.

Importantly, participants reflected positively on the Tandem process itself as a catalyst for knowledge exchange.

Recommendations:

Tandem should introduce structured processes to identify, assess, and strengthen the skills and capacities required for effective collaboration and coordination. Building on the DIRECTED peer-reviewed journal paper on *Capacity Development for Locally-Led Knowledge Co-Production Processes in Real World Labs for Managing Climate and Disaster Risk* (Cumiskey et al., 2025), Tandem can operationalize these insights by embedding self-assessment tools that enable participants to map existing capacities, identify areas requiring development or strengthening, and design targeted capacity-building plans.

The paper sets out a framework of four key capacities: collaborative, systems thinking, creative, and reflexive capacities, supported by related skills in design, research, and facilitation. The Tandem Modules already reflect this framework, with each module outlining how these capacities can be developed through applied practice.

Given that both “soft” capacities (e.g., collaboration) and technical skills (e.g., risk modelling) were repeatedly referenced in DIRECTED discussions, Tandem should facilitate processes that allow RWL members to assess current skills, identify gaps, and co-develop strategies for capacity strengthening ([Section 4](#)). This includes leveraging existing expertise through peer-to-peer learning and skill sharing, while also creating pathways to acquire new competencies. In doing so, Tandem can help participants move from diagnosing collaboration challenges to building the concrete capacities needed to sustain effective, multi-level, and cross-sectoral collaboration.

3.2.6 Monitoring, evaluation, and learning

The co-explore deductive code ‘Monitoring, evaluation, and learning’ revealed that in most RWLs, MEL is understood primarily as a post-event component of DRM, rather than being embedded as an ongoing way of working or as part of CCA processes. This indicates a narrow framing, where reflection and evaluation occur retrospectively after disasters, but are typically not systematically integrated into anticipatory planning, learning cycles, or adaptation strategies.

Within DIRECTED and through Tandem, however, MEL has been applied more broadly and early in the engagement process, particularly through efforts to evaluate individual capacity development, CCA actions in labs and the challenges they face. These exercises have provided insight into both the effectiveness of adaptation interventions and the barriers to their implementation.

The deductive code ‘Capacity Development Impact’ (7 references) demonstrated clear evidence of positive outcomes from DIRECTED’s workshop activities. Participants highlighted improved collaboration through workshops, increased understanding of risk management and climate resilience, and a greater ability to work with uncertainty.

Recommendations:

Within DIRECTED, Tandem monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) has been approached in two key ways: first, to monitor and evaluate ongoing capacity development, and second, to capture the outcomes of co-production. Moving forward, DIRECTED should strengthen MEL by consolidating these strands into a more coherent whole-project evaluation framework. This would mean systematically bringing together the diverse MEL activities already undertaken across the project to build a comprehensive picture of progress and impact.

In addition, MEL activities at the RWL level should be captured more formally through their theories of change, ensuring that lessons and outcomes are consistently documented. This would not only provide valuable inputs into the overarching project evaluation, but also complement and enrich the outputs of the application of Risk-Tandem (D3.2). Embedding these processes would allow DIRECTED to better track learning over time, assess the added value of co-production, and feed findings back into adaptive project management and the refinement of Tandem.

A key capacity highlighted in DIRECTED’s capacity development framework is reflexivity, the ability of RWL hosts and participants to critically reflect on their practices, assumptions, and outcomes. Reflexivity acts as a bridge between MEL and capacity development: while MEL provides the structures for documenting progress and outcomes, reflexivity enables the continuous questioning and adaptation of approaches. Together, they create the conditions for iterative learning, improved collaboration, and adaptive governance.

To operationalize this, Tandem should introduce formalized reflexivity processes at each stage of its methodology, ensuring that evaluation is not just retrospective but embedded in everyday RWL practices. This would allow reflexivity to be collectively captured and shared, reinforcing a culture of iterative learning and ensuring that MEL contributes directly to building the capacities needed for long-term resilience.

4 Tandem online modules update

These Tandem online Capacity Development Modules are our most recent update to Tandem. The modules build on lessons learned through a combination of:

- The iterative application of Tandem in DIRECTED
- The foundation and insights from the ToT workshop preparation and training sessions (including guidance documents, presentations, literature, and hands-on activities),
- Resources created and used in the RWLs
- Analysis of the results of the Capacity Needs Assessment
- DIRECTED document and reports coding analysis
- Ongoing scoping consultations with the labs

As a result, we have developed a comprehensive set of Capacity Development Modules for Tandem (which can be printed as PDFs for in-person facilitation or accessed on Miro for online delivery), and an updated online interactive Tandem tool, designed for easier click-through navigation of Tandem questions. All are available to explore on the weADAPT knowledge sharing platform (managed by SEI): <https://weadapt.org/tandem/>

The weADAPT platform is an openly accessible and free to use resource that facilitates learning on climate adaptation issues for both experienced practitioners, researchers, planners and policy makers, as well as those new to the field. Content is systematically organized by themes, networks, and categories, with linked tags to enhance knowledge interoperability in a coherent manner. The online interactive Tandem modules will be hosted on weADAPT, providing continuity and ensuring long-term legacy beyond the lifetime of DIRECTED. This means modules can also be continually refined and expanded as new examples test the guidance.

4.1 Developing Tandem Modules

The purpose of these modules ([Figure 8](#)) is to translate the tailored, project-specific training and diversity of approaches taken by each of the RWL hosts into a format that can be applied more widely, beyond the DIRECTED project to guide transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes

These modules are structured to reflect the core components of the Tandem Framework and to equip future facilitators, researchers, and practitioners with the skills and knowledge needed to support knowledge co-production in diverse settings.

The overview module introduces core co-production capacities (Cumiskey et al., 2025)-collaborative, systems thinking, creative, and reflexive - and links them to the practical skills of facilitation, design, and research. This module sets the foundation for engaging with the subsequent modules, each of which corresponds to one of the Tandem phases:

1. Scoping and review
2. Co-exploring 'What is'
3. Co-designing 'What if' and 'What next'

4. Integrating new knowledge and partners
5. Cross-cutting

Each module begins by describing how the core capacities are activated within that phase and provides tools and guidance to support implementation.

Figure 8: Overview of the Tandem capacity development training modules.

The modules therefore aim to serve as a legacy of the DIRECTED project - making the knowledge and methods developed through ToT sessions accessible to a broader community of practice and adaptable to new contexts. This will then be linked to the e-Learning modules specific to Risk-Tandem under development in D6.4.

4.1.1 Overview Module

This module was developed in response to the identified need for support across design, research, and facilitation within the labs. These needs emerged through one-to-one consultations with lab hosts, insights into the core capacities required for knowledge co-production, and lessons from previous applications of the Tandem Framework, explored further, in 'Capacity Development for Locally-Led Knowledge Co-Production Processes in Real World Labs for Managing Climate and Disaster Risk' (Cumiskey et al., 2025). The

module builds on the original Training of Trainers resources and Tandem’s cross-cutting elements - covering topics such as workshop design and facilitation, research basics, ethics, and monitoring, evaluation and learning (MEL) - but reorganizes this content within a structured framework focused on the three key skill areas: design, facilitation, and research.

4.1.2 Phase 1: Foundation Module

This module builds on the original guidance documents and one-to-one consultations focused on stakeholder identification and engagement, the training on risk scoping, and the facilitated theory of change exercises conducted with the RWL hosts. The module incorporates and adapts exercises from both the initial training activities and methods developed by the hosts for use within their RWLs. These adapted exercises, along with those proposed in earlier training, are outlined below with the original exercise on the left with the updated exercise sheets, referred to as ‘*Canvases*’, on the right. The canvases can also be viewed here:

<https://weadapt.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/Tandem-activity-canvases-.pdf>

Previously, this phase of the Tandem was referred to as Scoping. However, based on reflections from RWL hosts and insights from the coding, we have broadened its focus and renamed it Foundation, also to align with the Risk-Tandem Foundation phase. This shift acknowledges the wider range of needs involved in establishing a RWL. To support this, the Tandem Overview Module now includes practical guidance on setting up a transdisciplinary RWL, with particular emphasis on ensuring diverse participation and tailored citizen involvement.

4.1.2.1 Tandem challenges and goals scoping canvas

This resource ([Figure 10](#)) builds on the canvas used within the Danube RWL, Zala workshops March 2025 ([Figure 9](#)), which used storytelling and mapping to first consider past and future challenges before looking at goals and ideas for the future. Then the exercise asked participants to reflect on the barriers and enablers to these goals by using the mindset, behavioural, grassroutes and governance levels from the multi layer perspective framework (used within the co-explore Tandem phase).

Resource from training / RWL workshops

Figure 9: Canvas of Challenges and Goals scoping exercise used in Zala RWL 3 workshops March 2025

Final Tandem Modules resource

Figure 10: Tandem Modules resource: Tandem Challenges and Goals Scoping Canvas

4.1.2.2 Risk governance scoping canvas

This resource (Figure 12) builds on the Risk Governance exercise (Figure 11) conducted with the RWLs during the scoping phase ToT training online (June 2023) which aims to support RWLs in co-exploring their complex risk context (hazards, vulnerabilities, exposure) and risk governance using an online [Miro.com](https://miro.com) template. RWL hosts were tasked to identify a flood risk in their RWL and draw connections to the causes and drivers, influencing factors, vulnerabilities, resilience and adaptation measures and consider the role of uncertainty. RWL practitioner hosts were then invited to explore how this relates to their RWL governance context by reflecting on the stakeholders involved, communication challenges, risk knowledge and the institutional landscape. It responds to the coding recommendation, that ‘in order to better understand and facilitate the integration of DRR and CCA it is important that Tandem (supported by Risk-Tandem) explicitly probes the connections between hazards, exposure and vulnerability to understand sources of risk.’

Resource from training / RWL workshops

Figure 11: Capacity Development Risk Governance scoping Miro exercise, June 2023

Final Tandem Module resource

Figure 12: Tandem Modules resource: Risk Governance Scoping Canvas

In the updated exercise, we have added Tandem questions into this framing. Below you can see how the questions fit below the headings ‘Vulnerabilities and exposures’ and risks and impacts’. However, the heading ‘Hazards’ poses an opportunity for additional Tandem questions, supported by DIRECTED innovations to explore future hazards.

Vulnerabilities and exposures:

- What are the socio-economic challenges in the region, (including factors beyond the control of decision-makers) e.g. that affect access to or management of particular resources?
- Where are the most vulnerable areas and why are they vulnerable? Be open to vulnerability that is not necessarily related to climate. E.g., related to ecosystem services.

Risks and impacts:

- Do climate or weather events and impacts affect/exacerbate these vulnerabilities, and if so, in what way?
- What are the different communities and activities at risk? How does vulnerability differ amongst groups and activities? Why are they vulnerable? Be open to sources of vulnerability that are not necessarily related to climate. E.g., related to dynamic social vulnerability.

- Is there any risk of exacerbated vulnerability here or elsewhere, due to compound or cascading risks?

4.1.2.3 Tandem stakeholder analysis canvas

This resource ([Figure 14](#)) builds on the Mendelwes Stakeholder Matrix (1991) which was used during a Tandem ToT training session with RWL hosts ([Figure 13](#)). It is used to support the consideration of the following Tandem questions:

- Which groups are impacted on the ground (e.g. at community level) and can provide representative voice(s)?
- Which organizations, institutions or departments provide the relevant sectoral expertise and experience needed?
- Which (and whose) decisions and actions can influence the resilience of the system? Which actors are impacted by these issues, are vulnerable to them, or consider them important? What are the relationships between these actors?
- Are there multiple decision-makers at different scales, for whom different climate information (and formats) would be required based on the different types of decisions they are making? What methods of engagement (and communication styles/formats) are needed to ensure that the differentiated groups of actors identified, are engaged? E.g., socio-economic status, institution, knowledge type, gender, ethnicity, age, disability, race, religion etc?
- What key knowledge systems exist? Which actors hold relevant knowledge? Are there actors we need to engage, who bring different perspectives of local or indigenous knowledge or encompass different characteristics related to socio-economic status, institution, knowledge type, gender, ethnicity, age, disability, race, religion etc? Are they willing and able to share this knowledge? If not, how can this be facilitated e.g. with the support of intermediaries or boundary partners?
- What local organizations and initiatives are already working on issues of climate resilience and related issues? Are there partnership opportunities?

Resource from training / RWL workshops

Figure 13: Adaptation of Mendelow's power-interest matrix, Guidance Note on Stakeholder Selection for RWL set-up (January 2024)

Final Tandem Module resource

Figure 14: Tandem Modules resource: Tandem Stakeholder Analysis Canvas

The gap between meaningful citizen engagement and the emphasis on communication ([Section 3.2.3 Citizen engagement](#)) represents a key opportunity for future Tandem development. This could be advanced through both co-designed exercises and new Tandem questions that probe how citizen knowledge can be harnessed, how participation can be incentivised, and how representation can be embedded into risk governance and climate adaptation strategies.

4.1.2.4 Net-Map exercise

This exercise ([Figure 16](#)), initially proposed in the Tandem Guiding Questions Matrix, was incorporated into the modules to complement the DIRECTED stakeholder exercise ([Figure 15](#)) by explicitly addressing considerations of power, identifying synergies in goals, and responding to gaps revealed in the coding analysis.

In the RWLs, this mapping was done during the writing of D1.1 RWL Description and Set-up, in efforts to understand the composition of Labs, and the existing connections between stakeholders. Each lab produced their own version – however, they did not include a detailed analysis of the relationships and power relations between stakeholders involved. The Net-Map exercise aims to address this further.

Resource from training / RWL workshops

Figure 5: The Flowchart shows the relations between the involved stakeholders.

Figure 13: Relations between the involved stakeholders.

Figure 15: Examples of Net-Maps (stakeholder maps) produced by RWL hosts (see Deliverable 1.1), January 2024

Final Tandem Module resource

PHASE 1 FOUNDATION: IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS

Net-Map exercise

Net-Map is an interview-based mapping tool that helps people understand, visualize, discuss, and improve situations in which many different actors influence outcomes. By creating influence network maps, individuals and groups can clarify their own view of a situation, foster discussion, and develop a strategic approach to their networking activities. More specifically, Net-Map helps players to determine:

1. **what actors are involved in a given network,**
2. **how they are linked,**
3. **how influential they are, and**
4. **what their goals are.**

Equipment needed:

- Large sheets of paper for network map (one per interview, at least A3, better A2).
- Felt pens for drawing links (different colours according to different links).
- Adhesive paper as actor cards (sticky notes, [K91] possibly using different colours for different kinds of actors).
- Flat round stackable discs for building influence towers (e.g. checkers game pieces, bicycle spare parts).
- Actor figurines (different board game figures, optional but especially useful when working with illiterate interviewees).

Determining linkages, levels of influence, and goals allows users to be more strategic about how they act in these complex situations. It helps users to answer questions such as: Do you need to strengthen the links to an influential potential supporter (high influence, same goals)? Do you have to be aware of an influential actor who doesn't share your goals? Can increased networking help empower your dis-empowered beneficiaries? This low-tech and low-cost tool can be used when working with rural community members with low levels of formal education, as well as with policy makers or international development actors.

Net-Map step-by-step manual: short version (555 KB), detailed version in English (248 KB) and Portuguese (852 KB)/training slide show (876 KB) Available linked.

Figure 16: Tandem Modules resource: Net-Map exercise

4.1.2.5 Stakeholder Excel

This exercise ([Figure 17](#)) was provided to the RWLs to aid their stakeholder engagement plan. We have taken it forward to the Tandem Modules as a structured way ([Figure 18](#)) for any lab host to think about how they will build their lab.

Resource from training / RWL workshops

3.3 Develop an engagement plan

When stakeholders have been identified, a plan for engagement can be established. This is important to structure (and measure!) the process of outreach targeting potential collaborators, in efforts to maintain accountability and transparency during the process of establishing RWLs. In addition, partners from diverse sectors may have differing needs and expectations regarding communication which require discussion to avoid disappointments and mishaps.

SELECTING AN APPROACH

Qualities of the potential partner should inform approaches for engagement. Table 1. outlines some of these, followed by figure 2. Elaborating suitable techniques.

Potential partner	Overview	Opportunity/Challenge	Possible approaches	Time + Information required
Governmental (Regional)	At the EU level, there may be officials who have significant leverage over, and an understanding of DBR/CCA activities which may benefit the RWLs.	Opportunity to increase the potential impact of RWLs through leverage and knowledge. Most likely to lack time for frequent engagement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emphasise impact Advocate Consult (snowball) 	Low
Government (National)	As above, may hold significant leverage and influence in their context. Most likely willing to take part, particularly if beneficial for their priorities.	Opportunity to connect DIRECTED to national priorities and decision making. Source of information for data needs. Most likely to lack time for frequent engagement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emphasise impact Advocate Consult (snowball) 	Low
Government (sub-national/local)	Likely to hold share connections with local actors. Practical knowledge.	Opportunity to tap into local governance, priorities, and information. Most accessible group, with contributions to climate services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emphasise impact Advocate Consult (snowball) 	Low
Non-governmental (NGO/CSO)				Moderate
Private Sector (insurance, utility, construction etc.)				High
Communities and citizens				High

Project: 101073978 — DIRECTED — HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01 Funded by the European Union

Figure 17: Stakeholder Engagement Excel Guidance Note on Stakeholder Selection for RWL set-up (January 2024)

Final Tandem Module resource

PHASE 1 FOUNDATION: IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS

Stakeholder Excel

When stakeholders have been identified, a plan for engagement can be established. This is important to structure (and measure!) the process of outreach targeting potential collaborators, in efforts to maintain accountability and transparency during the process of establishing real world labs. In addition, partners from diverse sectors may have differing needs and expectations regarding communication, discussion of these issues may be needed to avoid disappointments and mishaps.

Organisation name	Mandate / objective	Focal point name	Contact information	Role	Engagement plan	Status of engagement	Sector	Decision making level	Interest	Power / influence	Additional information
					e.g. to be introduced by xxxx	e.g. introductory email sent	e.g. public services	e.g. regional	High / medium / low	High / medium / low	

52

Figure 18: Tandem Modules resource: Stakeholder Excel

4.1.2.6 Tandem aligning and trust building

Resource from training / RWL workshops

Figure 19: Canvas of Aligning exercise used in Zala RWL 3 workshops March 2025

Final Tandem Module resource

Figure 20: Tandem Modules resource: Tandem Aligning and Trust Building

This exercise ([Figure 20](#)) is an adaptation of an exercise done with the Zala RWL workshops, March 2025 ([Figure 19](#)). The exercise reveals opportunities for new Tandem questions which centre around aligning goals and visions in order to build strong foundations for the project. The questions incorporate thinking from community organizing which emphasizes the need to align around a collective goal and vision but also to align self interests and ensure that the project is beneficial for everyone involved.

The questions, to be further refined for Tandem, are:

- What do you think are the most important challenges for (insert area)?
 - What are the barriers to generating change?
- What's our vision for (insert area)?
 - What are the priorities for (insert area)?
- What are our personal / professional goals & expectations?
 - Consider what you want to get out of this experience! Are there skills or capacities you want to develop? Connections you would like to make? Organisations and communities you would like to introduce?
- What are our collective goals for this collaboration?
 - Considering our personal aims alongside the priorities for a collective future, what do we want to achieve through this collaboration?

This exercise ([Figure 21](#)) builds on the Capacity Needs Assessment conducted in RWL 1 (The Capital Region of Denmark) ([Figure 22](#)), but rather than adopting a deficit- or needs-based framing, it seeks to strengthen and amplify existing capacities and ways of working. The approach emphasizes leveraging what RWL participants are already doing well, while creating opportunities for peer-to-peer learning and exchange to deepen collective capacity.

Establishing ways of working

Final Tandem Module resource

Figure 23: Tandem Modules resource: Establishing Ways of Working

At the beginning of DIRECTED, a Guidance Note provided an overview of the initial Risk-Tandem Framework approach aiming to guide and support RWL to implement knowledge co-production processes to develop technical and governance solutions that integrate Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA), and support monitoring learning and evaluation. Graphics were provided via PowerPoint slides that could be used in RWL workshops to introduce the approach. However, within the Copenhagen General Assembly (September 2025) a common reflection within the consortium was the time needed to build relationships and establish ways of working at the start of a project. This process (Figure 23) aims to explicitly bring this to the forefront at the start of the project, building on the initial DIRECTED Guidance note, alongside the Tandem ‘Aligning and Trust Building’ canvas. It is then continued in the ‘Theory of Change’ canvas.

The activity aims to facilitate the exploration of existing Tandem questions in more manageable steps and responds to the Capacity Needs Assessment which called for:

- Opportunities to experiment safely and overcome organizational constraints that limit creative thinking.

4.1.2.8 Theory of change

Resource from training / RWL workshops

Figure 24: Canvas of Theory of Change exercise iteratively completed with RWLs

Final Tandem Module resource

Figure 25: Tandem Modules resource: Theory of Change

This activity ([Figure 25](#)) directly builds on multiple *Theory of Change* exercises that have been regularly referred back to with RWLs throughout the project. Within the modules this exercise is similarly framed as an iterative exercise to revisit after every Tandem phase. It aims to respond to the capacity needs requests to:

- Clarify the connection between RWL activities and research objectives.
- Improve the integration of monitoring, evaluation, and learning practices to capture lessons from co-production.

In the next Tandem update we will work to incorporate more of the cross-cutting MEL Tandem guiding questions into this exercise.

4.1.3 Phase 2: Co-exploring 'What is...' Module

This module builds on the training that was provided to each lab host to explore communication, governance, and technical challenges, as well as to identify additional stakeholders for engagement.

The first half of the module brings together the guidance sheets and insights from one-to-one consultations on conducting focus groups, workshops, and interviews. The second half draws on the Training of Trainers session on systems thinking and mapping, offering approaches for sensemaking the data and perspectives gathered during the research phase.

We frame this stage as the co-exploration of "what is" - an in-depth understanding of current challenges, governance dynamics, and stakeholder goals. This sets the stage for the next phase in the Tandem process, co-designing 'What if...', where we shift focus to the co-exploration of "what if" - imagining possible futures - and "what next" - mapping out the pathways to achieve them.

4.1.3.1 Co-exploring stakeholders

Resource from training / RWL workshops

Final Tandem Module resource

Figure 26 and 27: Target group and solution co-exploration exercise used in ToT RiskTandem training in March 2024 at the DIRECTED General Assembly

Figure 28: Tandem Modules resource: Co-Exploring Stakeholders

This exercise (Figure 28) builds directly on the stakeholder scoping conducted at the first General Assembly (Figure 26 & 27) and has since been embedded within the co-exploration phase, with additional prompts designed to capture stakeholders' mindsets, concerns, interests, and actions. These refinements respond to insights from the Capacity Needs Assessment, which highlighted the demand for:

- A clearer understanding of processes, structures, roles, responsibilities, and capabilities in order to identify opportunities for collaboration.
- Greater guidance on tools and frameworks that can systematically support creative practices within Real World Labs.
- Examples and structured approaches for embedding creativity into RWL activities in ways that are both practical and transferable.

Importantly, the exercise has been designed as an iterative process, allowing stakeholder mapping to evolve throughout the project. This reflexive approach ensures continuous consideration of who is missing, whose perspectives remain underrepresented, and how engagement strategies can be adapted to close those gaps.

4.1.3.2 Multi Layer Perspective Mapping

Resource from training / RWL workshops

Final Tandem Module resource

Figure 29: Multi Layer Perspective map exercise, 'From co-exploring to co-designing' ToT session, January 2025

	HISTORICAL EVOLUTION	CURRENT CONDITIONS	POSSIBLE FUTURE
ECOLOGICAL	Global factors impacting on or impacted by activity across other levels. This can include extreme events, change in climate, viral outbreaks, or wars.		
STRUCTURAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are there institutional / or policy relevant "barriers of adaptability", such as the general structure of the central sector or regulatory framework that can respond to regulatory uncertainty? Are there other knowledge systems that need to be considered and included in the design of the adaptation strategy, beyond local and traditional knowledge and experience? How can these be integrated or adapted? What are the knowledge and experience challenges that need to be addressed to ensure that the adaptation strategy is effective and resilient? How can the knowledge and experience challenges be addressed? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are the potential institutional and governance arrangements that are needed to support the adaptation strategy? Are there other knowledge systems that need to be considered and included in the design of the adaptation strategy, beyond local and traditional knowledge and experience? How can these be integrated or adapted? What are the knowledge and experience challenges that need to be addressed to ensure that the adaptation strategy is effective and resilient? How can the knowledge and experience challenges be addressed? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What current and proposed climate impacts, risks and opportunities are identified? How can these be integrated or adapted? What are the knowledge and experience challenges that need to be addressed to ensure that the adaptation strategy is effective and resilient? How can the knowledge and experience challenges be addressed?
MINDSET & IDEOLOGIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the agency and highlight of the adaptation challenge? Does public perception of the challenge and the need for action differ from what is the case? If so, how can this be addressed? What are the values and beliefs that underpin our ways of being and societal norms and rules? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are the predominant values and beliefs different across actors and how can they be used? If not, how can they be addressed? Why do they matter and how can they be used? 	
THE EVERYDAY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are the current and proposed climate impacts, risks and opportunities? How can these be integrated or adapted? What are the knowledge and experience challenges that need to be addressed to ensure that the adaptation strategy is effective and resilient? How can the knowledge and experience challenges be addressed? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are there existing climate related resources including institutional and governance arrangements that can be used to support the adaptation strategy? What are the knowledge and experience challenges that need to be addressed to ensure that the adaptation strategy is effective and resilient? How can the knowledge and experience challenges be addressed? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What climate risks or impact related are identified? How can these be integrated or adapted? What are the knowledge and experience challenges that need to be addressed to ensure that the adaptation strategy is effective and resilient? How can the knowledge and experience challenges be addressed?
EXPERIMENTAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the part of the system where grassroots work is happening. Experimental activity and innovation that challenge the norms are incubated here. 		

Figure 30: Tandem Modules resource: Historical Evolution Multi Layer Perspective Map

This exercise (Figure 30) builds on the Historical Evolution Multi Layer Perspective Map of Wallace (2021) with alterations to the language used to better suit the context of DIRECTED labs. Within DIRECTED, it provided an opportunity for labs to sensemake and systems map their reflections on Tandem questions which they had explored through primary and secondary data collection.

It responds to the coding findings, which prompted a recommendation that:

- Future Tandem iterations should prompt participants to consider both economic and ecological vulnerabilities, and how these interact under climate change. This could form the basis of broader risk-mapping questions, linking physical vulnerabilities to socio-economic and ecological systems. The mapping of systems will enable a coordinated DRR and CCA approach with explicit tagging of challenges, goals and ideas. New guiding questions should be accompanied by processes/exercises to guide Tandem users to connect across systems and understand drivers of risk to ensure that DRM plans align with CCA priorities, and that multi-hazard approaches are embedded across governance levels, sectors, and timescales.

As well as additional requests from the Capacity Needs Assessment which called for:

- Guidance on appropriate methods and questions to ask to integrate systems thinking effectively.
- Tools and ideas to better evaluate cascading impacts, uncertainty, and interactions across risks and climate change.

4.1.3.3 Multi Layer Perspective Mapping - Identifying potential leverage points

Resource from training / RWL workshops

Figure 31: Multi Layer Perspective map exercises, From co-exploring to co-designing' ToT session, January 2025

Final Tandem Module resource

Figure 32: Tandem Modules resource: Identifying Leverage Points Multi Layer Perspective Map

This exercise ([Figure 32](#)) builds on Wallace's (2021) Multi-Layer Perspective Map method, with adaptations in language to better fit the context of DIRECTED labs. In practice, RWL hosts applied "how might we..." provocations to surface leverage points across the system. This approach also opens the door for additional Tandem questions that encourage systems thinking and support the development of constellations of leverage points - ultimately fostering ecosystems of interventions. It responds to the Capacity Needs Assessment which called for:

- Advice on translating systems thinking into actionable approaches within risk management processes.

5 Next steps

The next step in the Capacity Development Modules and Tandem refinement is an emerging, demand-led process that will continue to evolve in response to RWL needs. This will involve iterative reflection on the work completed so far, incorporating the recommendations from this report, and developing processes to strengthen guidance for the co-design and Sustain phases of Tandem, both of which are already underway within the labs.

The co-design and Sustain phases (alongside associated modules) will build on prior ToT sessions, particularly those focused on rapid prototyping and creative methods to initiate co-design processes. They will also expand ongoing initiatives, including:

- The tabletop exercise co-designed with RWL 4 (Rhine-Erft)
- The further integration of Risk-Tandem and approaches such as the Multi-Criteria Analysis, through an exercise co-designed with RWL 1 (The Capital Region of Denmark)
- Further exploration of the assumptions related to data and models by RWL stakeholders and about the decision context by modellers (resulting in the finalization of D4.2 and the refinement of the Directed taxonomy)
- Creative ways to engage with citizens and collaborate with young people through the RWL 3 (Zala) climate festival
- Creative visioning explored with RWL 3 (Zala) through the Resilient West Balaton Region work as a method to evaluate and sustain interventions
- Further use of Multi-Level Perspective mapping to anticipate how projects can be sustained over time
- Using creative methods to deepen understanding of semantic variations and ambiguities in lab-related terminology, and to enhance clarity by integrating visual aids that support cross-cultural and interdisciplinary comprehension where language alone may cause misinterpretation

In addition, policy mapping and strategies for the exploitation of interventions will be advanced. A systems-thinking perspective will guide this work, helping to identify additional interventions needed to ensure sustainability or to complement and amplify existing efforts.

Below, we outline the key areas of recommendations that will guide this next stage.

5.1 Futures thinking

Futures thinking (Khun, 1977; Bell, 2003; Mansini, 2002) has been a central component of the Design Skills section of the Overview module. We see opportunities to use these approaches to strengthen the integration of DRM and CCA, advance multi-hazard and legacy risk management, and improve the communication of uncertainty. Work with labs has already begun to explore the question of “what is”, building on their analyses through systems thinking and multi-level perspective (MLP) mapping.

By combining systems thinking and futures thinking, Tandem will move beyond just guiding questions toward processes that enhance the learning capacity and adaptive resilience of real-world labs. This approach builds on the limited reference to the code “*Maladaptation Risks*” and aligns with what Wallace (2021) describes as the “real innovation” of a Complex Adaptive Systems’ (CAS) approach (Borkar et al., 2020; Hassan, 2014; Zivkovic, 2018). Tandem will introduce structured processes to systematically explore maladaptation and multi-risk interactions, expanding the existing guiding question: “*Are multiple risks (climate and non-climate) being considered, and is there potential for maladaptation, compound, or cascading effects across departments, sectors, or locations?*”

The approach will also help stakeholders explore long-term uncertainties, alternative adaptation pathways, and transition scenarios across multiple systems, while recognizing how historical contexts, such as land-use decisions, shape present and future vulnerabilities. We will apply this approach in the Zala RWL to build on earlier work envisioning a resilient West Balaton Region. The exercises developed for the Climate Festival in April 2026 will feed directly into the next Tandem refinement and the Capacity Development Modules. Similarly, in the Rhein-Erft RWL, we will explore how MLP mapping can support efforts to address the multiple risks of flooding and drought. Here, the exercise can be used to connect risk management with broader sustainability transitions, for example, aligning flood resilience with ecological restoration, risk-informed tourism, or climate-sensitive urban planning. This work aims to support cultural and institutional shifts from reactive crisis management toward anticipatory, long-term, and transformative resilience building.

In addition, by building on the Rhein-Erft tabletop exercise¹ and the multi-criteria analysis (MCA) exercises piloted with the Danish RWL, Tandem will support Risk-Tandem to formalize and expand these practices within identified governance processes.

5.2 Citizen engagement

As DIRECTED enters its final year, there is clear recognition that citizen engagement has not been as extensive as initially anticipated. However, the active efforts now underway across RWLs to trial alternative methods of engagement will generate valuable lessons, offering insight and evidence to inform the final Tandem update (D4.3). For example, the coding confirmed a persistent gap between meaningful citizen engagement and the current emphasis on communication, highlighting a key opportunity for future Tandem development. This could be advanced through co-designed exercises and new Tandem questions that explore how citizen knowledge can be harnessed, how participation can be incentivised, and how representation can be embedded within risk governance and climate adaptation strategies. Rather than relying on a deficit or needs-based framing, DIRECTED should build on, and strengthen, existing networks and practices, leveraging what communities are already doing. This approach is being applied in the Zala Region, where the upcoming

¹ <https://www.sei.org/perspectives/camaraderie-in-chaos/>

Climate Festival will reinforce existing citizen engagement by connecting with the HELIKON Student Arts Festival², a national event involving secondary students across diverse art forms. By working with the Mayor and the organisers to theme the festival around climate, and by running additional complementary workshops and events, we aim to expand participation and deepen engagement. These methods will provide valuable insights to inform the final update of Tandem and strengthen its capacity to embed citizen perspectives in climate resilience strategies.

5.3 Taxonomy development

The next version of the capacity development modules will feature an interactive glossary, building on the Climate Connectivity Taxonomy³ co-developed with RWLs and findings from D4.2. This glossary will prioritize terminology from the various models and tools feeding into the Data Fabric. The Hub will expand existing taxonomies with clear definitions and scope notes, helping RWL decision-makers better understand the Data Fabric and its outputs. The glossary will also be integrated into the online Tandem modules on weADAPT, enabling users to access definitions by hovering over specific concepts. The Taxonomy will be further developed through two ‘Designers in residence’, hosted by SEI. The residency aims to deepen understanding of semantic variations and ambiguities in lab-related terminology, and to enhance clarity by integrating visual aids that support cross-cultural and interdisciplinary comprehension where language alone may cause misinterpretation. The aim is to raise awareness and foster understanding of how the same terms may be interpreted differently across actors, disciplines, and fields.

Linking with the Taxonomy development we will further develop the work around the Assumptions Framework (D4.2), exploring relevant terms through scope notes for the Data Fabric. These are developed via conversations with RWL hosts and stakeholders, in efforts to compare modelling terms to their local usage and in consideration of issues of translation to Danish, Italian, German and Hungarian.

5.4 Monitoring, evaluation, and learning

Tandem should continue embedding formalised reflexivity processes within each phase of its methodology, ensuring that monitoring and evaluation (MEL) are not only retrospective but

² <https://helikoniunnepsegek.hu/>

³ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uPh00X7Et_E4Wsp4tgelurVzxPW4gsuEXY136ghXTzc/edit?tab=t.0

also integrated into the everyday practices of the labs. Reflexivity should be understood as both a capacity and a process, enabling lab hosts and participants to critically reflect on their practices, adapt approaches in real time, and capture evolving insights for long-term learning.

The updated Tandem and Capacity Development Modules can build on existing self-assessment tools by packaging them into structured exercises. These should enable participants to map current skills and capacities, identify gaps, and co-develop strategies for targeted strengthening. Given that both soft capacities (e.g., collaboration, communication) and technical skills (e.g., risk modelling, data management) were repeatedly referenced in DIRECTED discussions, Tandem should systematically track these dimensions across project phases to ensure ongoing capacity development.

Peer-to-peer learning mechanisms, piloted within DIRECTED and highly valued by participants, should be institutionalised as a core feature of Tandem. The inductive code Knowledge Sharing reinforced the demand for exchanges both within and across organisations, particularly between DRM and CCA professionals. Embedding structured peer-reflection sessions within and across RWLs would create spaces to compare experiences, challenge assumptions, identify shared challenges, and surface systemic lessons.

Finally, Tandem should continue to integrate reflexive insights into wider DIRECTED MEL reporting templates. Embedding these insights into project-wide evaluation, the e-Learning platform, and the evolving Risk-Tandem Framework will ensure that MEL is not treated as an add-on but as a driver of adaptation and innovation. This integration will also be particularly valuable for the Capacity Development modules in the sustain phase and for strengthening the cross-cutting dimensions of Tandem.

The [Tandem modules](#) will be available on the e-Learning Platform as part of a suite of learning programs and related DIRECTED resources and tools. The e-Learning Platform will be hosted on the weADAPT knowledge sharing platform (managed by SEI).

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Annex 1 Structured capacity needs assessment

This capacity needs assessment represents an elaboration of the semi-structured interviews, conducted and revised annually to identify emerging needs and RWL priorities. Although linked to capacities as detailed in table 1. (and the Risk-Tandem implementation in general), this draft should not be treated as the final product, but instead a foundation for capacity needs assessments, modules, and MEL for capacity development.

Introduction

As part of the capacity development for RWL hosts, this assessment seeks to identify and support the analysis of current work-flows and risk governance in DRR/CCA contexts toward improved integration. It was drafted to help determine the capacity needs and gaps for RWL hosts to develop during the capacity development. Building on the capacity development needs to be identified in this capacity needs assessment, trainings will be planned and designed to support capacity development of RWL hosts/trainers in co-production. The capacity needs assessments will be conducted throughout the DIRECTED project, to help inform future capacity development training.

Questionnaires

There will be one questionnaire (capacity needs assessment) asked to RWL hosts before their RWL workshops. For evaluation purposes, this will be combined with the co-production Capacity Development MEL questionnaires DIRECTED following capacity development activities.

Consent: Adhering to GDPR rules, all survey responses are confidential. We collect specific identity details only to help understand the demographic we have reached. The data from this survey will be used for scientific purposes within the DIRECTED project. The analysis of the survey data will be therefore anonymous and aggregated.

Please confirm the following statements* (MCQ):

I have read and understood the information provided above. I voluntarily consent to participate in this survey. Yes No

I consent to the processing of my anonymous data for research purposes* (SOQ)
Yes No

I confirm that I am 18 years or older* (SOQ) Yes No

A) Background questions:

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
1	Name	OQ	NA	NA
2	Job role/title	OQ	NA	NA
3	Role within RWLs	SOQ	Host; Participant; Facilitator	NA
4	Sector	SOQ	Research; Practitioner; I/NGO; Academia; Private; Civil service; Labourer	NA
5	Gender	SOQ	Female; Male; Other; Prefer not to say	NA

B) Questionnaire before capacity development

Questions on Transdisciplinary knowledge co-production

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
Understanding	How would you describe “knowledge co-production” in a few words?	OQ	NA
	What do you consider as the benefits of co-production to your work (in a few words)	OQ	NA
Experience	Have you collaborated with CCA practitioners before DIRECTED?	SOQ	1. Not at all – I have no prior experience 2. A little – I have collaborated with CCA practitioners occasionally 3. Somewhat – I have collaborated with CCA practitioners in certain projects or tasks but not extensively 4. Quite a bit – I regularly collaborated with CCA practitioners in my work
	Have you done any co-production work before DIRECTED?	SOQ	1. None 2. Participated/supported 3. Regularly participated and supported 4. Facilitated 5. Regularly Facilitated
	Please describe what co-production work you have previously done?	OQ	

Value	What were your expectations regarding co-production before you started DIRECTED?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very negative – I was skeptical and didn't believe it would be effective 2. Negative – I had doubts and wasn't confident in the process 3. Neutral – I wasn't sure what to expect, but open to it 4. Positive – I was optimistic about the process and outcomes 5. Very positive – I was excited and confident it would work well 6. N/A - I didn't know about co-production
	To what extent do you consider knowledge co-production processes as valuable?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not valuable at all – I don't believe it is needed 2. Neutral – I am unsure about the value of co-design 3. Few benefits – I see its potential but have significant doubts 4. Quite valuable – I think it can be beneficial for my work 5. Extremely valuable – I believe it is essential and highly effective mode of working
Evaluation	Please describe how DIRECTED has supported your capability to enable collaboration and knowledge co-production in your RWL?	OQ	NA
	How has DIRECTED helped you in promoting collaboration between DRR/CCA? Please describe	OQ	NA
	What have been the primary challenges to enabling collaboration and knowledge co-production in your RWL?	OQ	NA

Questions on Facilitation Skills

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
Experience	How would you rank your confidence to facilitate co-production workshops before DIRECTED?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I had little to no knowledge or confidence 2. Low – I had some confidence, but felt unsure 3. Moderate – I was somewhat confident, but there was room for growth 4. High – I was confident in my ability to enable knowledge co-production

			5. Very high - I was extremely confident and capable
	How would you rank your skills in facilitating creative/interactive methods before DIRECTED?	SOQ	1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for improvement 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
Current Skills / Capability	How would you rank your confidence to facilitate co-production workshops?	SOQ	1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or knowledge of how to facilitate co-production workshops 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability to enable knowledge co-production 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
	How would you rank your ability to listen to participants?	SOQ	1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
	How would you rank your ability to manage potential conflicts in RWLs?	SOQ	1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
	How would you rank your ability to facilitate discussions?	SOQ	1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
Evaluation	To what extent has DIRECTED increased your skills in bridging available risk/climate data and your stakeholders' needs?	SOQ	1. Not at all – the project has not contributed 2. A small extent – my skills have improved slightly 3. Moderately improved – room for growth 4. Large extent – greatly enhanced my skills 5. Very large extent – greatly enhanced my skills in bridging data and needs

	To what degree has DIRECTED increased your skills in facilitating creative and interactive activities?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all – it has not contributed 2. A small extent – my skills have improved slightly 3. A moderate extent – my skills have improved, but there is room for growth 4. A large extent – my skills have improved significantly 5. A very large extent – greatly enhanced my skills in facilitating them
	What further support do you need now to facilitate knowledge co-production?	OQ	NA

Questions on Research Skills

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
Experience	To what extent have you done research before DIRECTED?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No experience 2. Participated/supported research 3. Regularly participated and supported research 4. Led/designed research for project purposes 5. Regularly led/designed research for project purposes
	Please describe your past research experience/methods used in few words.	OQ	NA
Value	To what extent do you consider qualitative methods valuable and/or useful to further understand your stakeholders' needs? (Interviews, surveys, etc).	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not valuable at all 2. Somewhat valuable – I'm unsure about their usefulness 3. Neutral – I see the potential but have doubts 4. Quite valuable – I think qualitative research helps in many situations 5. Extremely valuable – I believe qualitative research is essential for understanding RWL needs
Current Skills / Capabilities	Are you confident in enabling, leading or applying qualitative research/methods in your RWLs independently?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for improvement 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable

	How would you rank your ability to lead surveys, interviews or focus group discussions?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for improvement 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
	How would you rank your skills to manage and collect data (transcripts, workshop outcomes, survey results)	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for improvement 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
	How would you rank your ability to Monitor, Evaluate and Learn (from) the knowledge co-production process?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
Evaluation	To what degree has DIRECTED increased your skills in conducting research?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all – the project has not contributed to my skills 2. To a small extent – my skills have improved slightly 3. To moderate extent – my skills have improved, but there is room for growth 4. To a large extent – my skills have improved significantly 5. To a very large extent – greatly enhanced my skills
	What further support or skills do you need for leading research in your RWL?	OQ	NA

Questions on Design Skills

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
Understanding	What does "design thinking" mean in your context/RWL?	OQ	NA
Experience	To what extent have you used design processes and creative methods before DIRECTED?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all – I have no prior experience with design processes and creative methods in my work 2. A little – I have used design processes and creative methods occasionally but without a structured approach 3. Somewhat – I have used design processes and creative methods in certain projects or tasks, but not extensively

			4. Quite a bit – I regularly used design processes and creative principles in my work
	Please describe how you have used design processes and creative methods before DIRECTED	OQ	NA
Value	To what extent do you consider design thinking helpful or valuable to your day to day work?	SOQ	1. Not valuable at all 2. Neutral – I don't have an opinion 3. Slightly valuable – I see some potential but have significant doubts 4. Quite valuable – I think it can be beneficial for many situations 5. Extremely valuable – it is essential for my day to day work
	To what extent do you consider design processes and creative methods useful in your RWL context?	SOQ	1. Not valuable at all 2. Neutral – I don't have an opinion 3. Slightly valuable – I see some potential but have significant doubts 4. Quite valuable – I think it can be beneficial for many situations 5. Extremely valuable – it is essential for my day to day work
Current skills / capabilities	How would you rank your ability to design knowledge co-production processes?	SOQ	1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
	How would you rank your skills in utilising design thinking in your day-to-day work?	SOQ	1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
Evaluation	To what extent has DIRECTED increased your capacity in design thinking?		1. Not at all – the project has not contributed 2. To a small extent – my skills have improved slightly 3. Moderately improved – room for growth 4. Large extent – greatly enhanced my skills 5. Very large extent – greatly enhanced my skills

Questions on Systems Thinking capacity

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
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Understanding	What does "systems thinking" mean in your context/RWL?	OQ	NA
Experience	To what extent have you employed systems thinking in your work before DIRECTED?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all – I have no prior experience with design processes and creative methods in my work 2. A little – I have used design processes and creative methods occasionally but without a structured approach 3. Somewhat – I have used design processes and creative methods in certain projects or tasks but not extensively 4. Quite a bit – I regularly used design processes and creative principles in my work
	How would you rank your skills in utilising systems thinking in your day-to-day work?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
Value	To what extent do you consider systems thinking helpful or valuable to your day to day work?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not valuable at all 2. Neutral – I don't have an opinion 3. Slightly valuable – I see some potential but have significant doubts 4. Quite valuable – I think it can be beneficial for many situations 5. Extremely valuable – it is essential for my day to day work
Current Skills / Capabilities	How would you rank your skills to understand complexity and interconnectedness between disaster risk and climate change?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
	How would you rank your skills to communicate complexity with risks and climate change?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
	How would you rank your skills in conducting risk assessments that integrate risk reduction and Climate Change Adaptation, or consider cascading impacts?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable

	How would you rank your skills in developing/using risk scenarios in workshops?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
Evaluation	To what extent has DIRECTED increased your skills in systems thinking (for example, in terms of seeing connections between disciplines, risks and climate change)	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all – I have no prior experience with design processes and creative methods in my work 2. A little – I have used design processes and creative methods occasionally but without a structured approach 3. Somewhat – I have used design processes and creative methods in certain projects or tasks but not extensively 4. Quite a bit – I regularly used design processes and creative principles in my work
	What support/tools or ideas do you need to further promote systems thinking in your RWLs? For example, in terms of understanding cascading impacts, uncertainty, or the integration of climate change considerations into risk management?	OQ	NA
	Is there further support you may need to further promote the integration of climate change considerations into your current risk management approaches?	OQ	NA

Questions on Relationship building capacity

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
Current Skills / Capabilities	How would you rank your ability to build trust and relationships between stakeholders?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable

	How would you rank your ability to create open and safe spaces for stakeholder discussions?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
Experience	To what extent has DIRECTED increased your capacity to build relationships?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all – I have no prior experience with design processes and creative methods in my work 2. A little – I have used design processes and creative methods occasionally but without a structured approach 3. Somewhat – I have used design processes and creative methods in certain projects or tasks, but not extensively 4. Quite a bit – I regularly used design processes and creative principles in my work
	What knowledge or skills would help you in identifying opportunities for promoting collaboration between DRM/DRR/CCA actors, or between modellers and stakeholders?	OQ	NA

Questions on Reflexive Capacity

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
Understanding	In your opinion, what are the key skills or attributes required for reflective capacity? (e.g. Critical Thinking, Self-awareness, Empathy, Open-mindedness, etc.)	OQ	NA
Experience	How often do you engage in reflection about your work, decisions, or actions?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Never 2. Occasionally 3. Sometimes 4. Regularly 5. Always
Value	How valuable do you think reflective capacity is in your professional or personal life?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not valuable at all 2. Neutral – I don't have an opinion 3. Slightly valuable – I see some potential but have significant doubts 4. Quite valuable – I think it can be beneficial for many situations 5. Extremely valuable – it is essential for my day to day work
Current Skills / Capabilities	How confident are you in your ability to critically reflect on your own actions,	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure

	assumptions, and decisions?		3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
	In what contexts do you find it most challenging to be reflexive? (e.g. Under time pressure, In group settings, During crises, Other)	OQ	NA
Evaluation	To what extent has DIRECTED increased your reflexive capacity?	OQ	1. Not at all – the project has not contributed 2. To a small extent – my skills have improved slightly 3. Moderately improved – room for growth 4. Large extent – greatly enhanced my skills 5. Very large extent – greatly enhanced my skills
	Do you feel you have sufficient tools or frameworks to support reflective practices? If yes, which resources have helped you? If no, what additional resources would be helpful?	OQ	NA

Questions for Creative capacity

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
Understanding	In your opinion, what are the key skills or attributes required for creative capacity? (e.g: Imagination, Problem-solving, Open-mindedness, Experimentation, Other)	OQ	NA
Experience	How often do you engage in creative thinking or problem-solving in your personal or professional life?	SOQ	1. Never 2. Occasionally 3. Sometimes 4. Regularly 5. Always
Value	How valuable do you think creative capacity is in your professional or personal life?	SOQ	1. Not valuable at all 2. Neutral – I don't have an opinion 3. Slightly valuable – I see some potential but have significant doubts 4. Quite valuable – I think it can be beneficial for many situations 5. Extremely valuable – it is essential for my day to day work

Current Skills / Capabilities	How confident are you in your ability to generate innovative ideas or approaches?		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Very low – I have little to no confidence or ability 2. Low – I have some confidence, but still feeling unsure 3. Moderate – I am somewhat confident, but room for growth 4. High – I am confident in my ability 5. Very high – I am extremely confident and capable
	What do you see as the biggest barriers to expressing or developing your creativity? (E.g: Lack of time, Rigid processes, Fear of failure, Lack of support, Other)	OQ	NA
	What practices or activities do you use to nurture your creativity? (E.g: Brainstorming, Journaling, Mind-mapping, Creative hobbies, Other)	OQ	NA
Evaluation	To what extent has DIRECTED increased your creative capacity?	SOQ	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all – the project has not contributed 2. To a small extent – my skills have improved slightly 3. Moderately improved – room for growth 4. Large extent – greatly enhanced my skills 5. Very large extent – greatly enhanced my skills
	Do you feel you have sufficient tools or frameworks to support creative practices? If yes, which resources have helped you? If no, what additional resources would be helpful?	OQ	NA

Questions on Technical competency

Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
Have you worked with climate data and models before DIRECTED?	SOQ	1. Not at all – I have no prior experience 2. A little – I have used climate data and models occasionally 3. Somewhat – I have worked with climate data and models in certain projects or tasks but not extensively 4. Quite a bit – I regularly used climate data and models in my work
Are there any “hard” capacities or skills you would require to support your RWLs? May include topics such as risk communication, data visualisation, risk assessments, etc.	OQ	NA

Questions for Feedback on DIRECTED

Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
To what extent do you consider DIRECTED to be a valuable experience?	SOQ	1. Not valuable at all 2. Neutral – I don't have an opinion 3. Slightly valuable – I see some potential but have significant doubts 4. Quite valuable – I think it can be beneficial for many situations 5. Extremely valuable – it is essential for my day to day work
To what extent has DIRECTED affected your ways of working?	SOQ	1. Not at all 2. A little – small impact 3. Moderately – has made a noticeable difference in my ways of working 4. A lot – it has significantly influenced my ways of working and thinking 5. Completely – the project has transformed the ways in which I work, introducing meaningful changes
Are there any experiences or elements of the project that have been particularly valuable?	OQ	NA
Are there any experiences or elements that have been particularly disappointing?	OQ	NA
During the project, have you used other skills or knowledge in your RWLs, not covered in this questionnaire?	OQ	NA

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
6	Do you know what “co-production” is?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	NA
6a	Please select the statement which best defines “co-production”	SOQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An iterative and collaborative process involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways toward sustainable future. • A process that ensures participants work individually and separately on a project, with limited interaction between participants. • A process that highlights the best ways to work with stakeholders and stakeholders are encouraged to agree without providing feedback. 	Select “Yes” to Q6 above.
7	Have you done any co-production work previously?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	If select “Yes” to Q7 and “No” or “Not sure” to Q6 pop-up asking if they’re sure
8	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
8a	How is your knowledge of co-production?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8b	How confident are you at leading an activity in a workshop?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8c	How confident are you in leading an activity at a workshop if it is a co-production activity?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
9	Please select the correct definition for the following terms, relating to co-production			
9a	Stakeholder engagement	SOQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The actions, processes and procedures relating to engaging stakeholders. • Communications are led from the stakeholders who reach out to the project to ask to be involved. • The actions and processes related to ensuring people are unaware of the project and do not engage. 	NA

9b	Capacities	SOQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard and soft human capacities (knowledge and skills) required. • Plans to complete a project successfully. • Worst case scenario plans for a project. 	NA
9c	Knowledge integration	SOQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversification of available knowledge beyond a single discipline or epistemology, and their combination toward holistic understanding. • Ensuring only one key knowledge discipline is considered and used as the main focus. • Everyone contributes and co-produces information. 	NA
10	Please identify the benefits of co-production	MCQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased buy-in and ownership • Useful feedback and solutions • Excess feedback and solutions • Lack of buy-in and ownership • Builds on peoples existing capabilities • Breaks down barriers • Strengthens peer support networks • Builds mutuality and reciprocity • Builds gaps in knowledge • Builds barriers between people • Weakens communication and support networks • Creates separate work streams 	NA
11	Please identify the challenges of co-production	MCQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of engagement • Too much engagement • Limited facilitation in workshops • Too much facilitation in workshops • Stakeholder fatigue • Lack of time to complete work • Too much time taken to complete work • Language barriers 	NA

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited capacity • Communication challenges • Coordination challenges • Lack of resources 	
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General

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
12	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
12a	How would you rate your understanding of risk?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12b	How confident are you in explaining the concept of risk to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12c	How would you rate your understanding of risk governance?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12d	How confident are you in explaining the concept of risk governance to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12e	How would you rate your understanding of risk management?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12f	How confident are you in explaining the concept of risk management to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12g	How would you rate your understanding of stakeholder engagement?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12h	How confident are you in explaining the concept of stakeholder engagement to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12i	How would you rate your understanding of project financials?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12j	How confident are you in explaining the concept of project financials to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12k	How would you rate your understanding of data interoperability?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12l	How confident are you in explaining the concept of data interoperability to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA

12m	How would you rate your facilitation skills?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
13	Please put in order the topics you would like capacity development training on, with the highest priority first.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Risk and risk governance ● Co-production and transdisciplinary collaboration ● Risk management ● Communication and stakeholder engagement ● Finance ● Data interoperability ● Facilitation skills 	NA
14	What else do you hope to learn from the capacity development?	OQ	NA	NA

Partners

